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Table of contents

Abbreviations	5
Summary	6
Introduction	7
Graphical search tools in the NanoCommons KB	8
General features of the BioXM knowledge portals providing the GUI to the NanoCommons KB	8
Logging in	8
Navigating the interface	9
Using search forms	9
Working with tables	10
Searching in tables/result sets	10
Exporting	11
Exporting results from a table	11
Retrieving an export executed in the background	11
Working with the Actions menu	11
Working with panels	12
Working with graphs	12
Data access using the GUI of the NanoCommons Knowledge Base	13
General Search	13
Data Access	13
Particles	14
Characterisation data	17
Toxicology	18
Parameters	21
Data retrieval from NanoCommons KB to the Jaqpot modelling environment	22
Initial steps	22
Import/install necessary packages for communication with NanoCommons KB	22
Setting up a communication session with the NanoCommons KB	23
Queries and data retrieval from the NanoCommons KB	24
Retrieving Characterisation data from the NanoCommons KB	24
Retrieving the toxicity data from the NanoCommons KB	28
Handling the data for modelling	30
Import/install necessary packages for preprocessing, modelling and uploading to Jaqpot	30

Preprocessing Characterisation data for use in modelling	31
Isolating the toxicity endpoint from toxicity dataset	33
Preprocessing toxicity data for use as modelling endpoint values	35
Model development and validation	38
Uploading the predictive model to Jaqpot	42
Setting up Jaqpot	42
Uploading model to Jaqpot- From model to web service	42
Generating predictions from a Jaqpot model	43
NanoCommons Knowledge Base access within KNIME through Enalos APIs	45
Extracting datasets from NanoCommons KB within KNIME through Enalos APIs	46
Enalos APIs for NanoCommons Knowledgebase	51
Data retrieval from eNanoMapper instances	55
Similarity search tools	56
Import the required packages	57
Json / Python Dictionary query	57
Searching services in the Jaqpot modelling platform	61
Architecture of the Jaqpot search service	61
Description of Indexing	62
Description of the search service	63
Examples of using the Jaqpot search service	66
Semantic query and text mining	69
Installation and Setup	69
Semantic Querying and Label Expansion	69
Abstract Download	70
Metadata Download	72
Annotation and Labelling	73
Automating Mining Pipelines	75
Concept Relationship Summaries	76
Axiom Suggestion	77
Searching with identifiers	78
Conclusions	82
References	83
Appendix 1. Python functions developed for the NanoCommons similarity search tool	84

D4.6 Description of tools for automated data mining

Convert strings to numerical features / categories	84
Prepare the query	84
Similarity search function	84
Appendix 2. Definition of distance metrics in the NanoCommons similarity search tool	86

Abbreviations

API: Application Programming Interface

DLS: Dynamic light scattering

EBI: European Bioinformatics Institute

GUI: Graphical User Interface

HGNC: HUGO Gene Nomenclature Committee

HTTP: Hypertext Transfer Protocol

ID: Identifier

IRI: Internationalized Resource Identifier

JSON: JavaScript Object Notation

KB: Knowledge Base

NM: Nanomaterial

OWL: W3C Web Ontology Language

PBPK: Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic

PDB: Protein Data Bank

PMC: PubMed Central

QSAR: Quantitative Structure Activity Relationships

RAM: Random access memory

RDF: Resource Description Framework

REST: representational state transfer

RO: Relation Ontology

RSS: Rich Site Summary

SD: Standard deviation

UI: User interface

URL: Uniform Resource Locator

Summary

The NanoCommons Knowledge Base (KB) consists of a variety of data sources and data analysis and modelling tools, integrated under an agreed ontology and set of Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). Data search and retrieval tools and text mining services are important components of the KB, allowing end-users to perform various types of queries and searches for tools that are most suited to their modelling and analysis needs. These search tools can also increase the efficiency of service integration and interoperability by ensuring that the most relevant data are extracted from the KB and exchanged between the different services. This optimises interoperability, transfer and exchange of data and facilitates data-driven model building, which is based on the concept of nanomaterial (NM) similarity.

In this deliverable, we present the tools and services developed to date for automatic data and text mining and being offered for Transnational Access (TA) through the NanoCommons KB. The tools allow searching for both data, from primary data source (raw, processed and simulated) and curated from literature, and modelling resources. A user can search, for example, for all data relative to a specific type of NM, but also for models predicting properties, toxicology endpoints and biokinetic behavior of this type of NM. Furthermore, ontology-enabled search provides access to identified synonyms for key terms and mining of text to extract meaningful results.

More specifically, this Deliverable report contains descriptions of the following data search and data mining tools and services:

- The NanoCommons KB data section currently provides access to NMs, their physicochemical characterisation and classical or omics-based toxicological assessments. Searches can be executed either interactively in the graphical user interface (GUI) by accessing the web portal, or are software-based by accessing the REST web service API. They can be based on any attribute (data or metadata) assigned to a NM or measurement. The predefined user interface (UI) reports allow viewing and exporting of search results. In addition, the API allows defined searches and attributes to be exported to XML.
- Data search results from the NanoCommons KB can be communicated to third-party open source computational frameworks over APIs. We demonstrate how data can be transferred to the Jaqpot and the Enalos platforms and can subsequently be used to produce predictive models, which are accessible instantly as web services over APIs or GUIs via NanoCommons.
- Tools that apply similarity search to NMs were developed and deployed as part of WP4's Joint Research Activities (JRA). These enable identification of compounds similar to those defined initially, according to specified metric(s) and parameter(s). This helps the community make better use of available data, increases the validity of data and supports data analysis.
- A search mechanism, similar to that for data, has been developed and integrated in the Jaqpot modelling platform that allows users to query for models, algorithms or specific end-points that are applicable to specific NMs or end-points.
- The use of the eNanoMapper ontology as source of synonyms for domain specific terms and of related terms using the ontology hierarchy, and use the additional search strings in text mining was demonstrated. Furthermore, the use of NM identifiers to support text mining and integration with a literature database is described. These approaches are being prepared as

TA offers.

1. Introduction

The NanoCommons knowledge infrastructure contains a variety of software tools for data storage, management, integration and analysis, predictive model development and validation, automatic feature calculation, image analysis, data visualization, ontology annotation and safe-by-design. A systematic and searchable catalogue of the services available to the community via the NanoCommons infrastructure is provided to users through a dedicated web page <https://infrastructure.nanocommons.eu/services/>. Progress on development, extension and integration of these tools has been described in other deliverables. In particular, the KB specification and design was described in Deliverable D4.1 and the first version of the KB implemented using the BioXM Knowledge Management Environment was reported in Deliverable D4.4. In Deliverable 5.4 we demonstrated the two modelling platforms that have been integrated into the NanoCommons infrastructure, namely Jaqpot and Enalos, which are being developed and extended by partners NTUA and NovaM respectively.

The efficient use of the tools and services by end-users, but also integration and cross-linking between tools and third-party services can be facilitated through ontological annotations and smart search tools. Development and extension of the eNanoMapper ontology towards a general nanosafety ontology has been described in Deliverable D4.3. The current deliverable, D4.6 presents the progress and the current results in Task 4.3 and Task 4.4 of the project, which deal with the development of tools for data search and retrieval and for text mining and curation. Development of these tools addressed the need for interoperability among services, but also human interaction with the NanoCommons KB.

We demonstrate how software tools are able to communicate seamlessly with the NanoCommons KB to retrieve data in suitable forms for further processing and analysis. We illustrate how filters can be applied to retrieve the most relevant data, which greatly accelerates and optimises the processes of data analysis and model development. In a similar fashion, we present tools that have been developed within the project which allow end-users to perform smart searches through the NanoCommons and other integrated data warehouses and software tools, and receive concrete and accurate answers to their queries.

The tools presented in this deliverable are critical for the sustainability of the project results and outcomes and for the acceptance of the NanoCommons knowledge infrastructure by the nanosafety community. Development and integration of automated data mining tools can increase the efficiency and improve user experiences in terms of accessing specific services and the complete integrated NanoCommons infrastructure. Automated data mining tools can also contribute to attracting third-party data owners and model developers to integrate and offer their resources through the NanoCommons infrastructure, a key goal for the second half of the project.

2. Graphical search tools in the NanoCommons KB

Probably the most important entry point for users to the NanoCommons KB, at least if they are less experienced with the programming and e-infrastructure tools at the beginning of their interactions, is the GUI. Therefore, we start with the description of the GUI based search tools implemented in the NanoCommons KB. For a description of the API usage of the tools please refer to the relevant sections on data retrieval from the NanoCommons KB using the Jaqpot modelling platform (Section 3) or via KNIME through Enalos APIs (Section 4) below.

The NanoCommons KB is based on the BioXM Knowledge Management Environment. Therefore, the description of the search tools is done in two sections: 1) the generic functionality as supported by the Framework and 2) specific functions as configured for the NanoCommons KB.

2.1. General features of the BioXM knowledge portals providing the GUI to the NanoCommons KB

This section covers the general functionalities of the BioXM knowledge portal. Because the interface is highly flexible, differences in KBs are supported. Specific information about KBs are available in Section 2.2.

2.1.1. Logging in

Complete the following steps to login into a BioXM web portal:

1. Open a browser (Google Chrome®, Firefox® or Safari® browsers are recommended) and enter the uniform resource locator (URL) for the corresponding BioXM web portal (<https://ssl.biomax.de/nanocommons>). The login page will be displayed.
2. Enter your user name and password.
3. Click the "Login" button.
4. If you have not yet registered to the system click the "Please register here" link for autoregistration and provide a user name as well as a valid email.

The NanoCommons Knowledge Base web portal homepage will be displayed as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Homepage of the NanoCommons Knowledge Base portal

2.1.2. Navigating the interface

The BioXM web portal interface provides access to all content, resources and tools available for the specific installation. The interface is highly flexible, but in general, can be divided into the three areas visible in Figure 1:

- Navigation menu (on the left) provides links to content, resources and datasets available.
- Content panel (the main part of the window) contains the content, resource or dataset that has been selected. Additional navigation items can be accommodated if needed. The blue text items, buttons and icons are, in most cases, links to related information.
- Toolbar (near the upper right corner) provides additional buttons to general actions, such as printing the current page or logging out.

Click one of the buttons to perform the desired action.

2.1.3. Using search forms

Several search forms are available for starting a query or search. Specific instructions are readily available in the individual search forms. In general, complete the following steps to start a search:

1. Enter the desired term(s) in the search field(s) or select from drop-down lists. To see all results, enter an asterisk (*) in the field. Click the "x" button to clear the search fields.
2. Click the "Search" button.

The search results (result set) will be displayed, as per the example in Figure 2. The search can be refined directly in the result set (see section 2.1.5).

Toxicity: Search

Figure 2. Using search forms - Search form with text field and drop-down list.

2.1.4. Working with tables

Search results and other information are often displayed on a table. This section describes working with tables in the BioXM system in general. The actions available in individual tables may vary.

In most tables, several actions can be performed directly:

- Display all columns (potentially hidden on small screens e.g. mobile devices) by clicking the "+" sign at the beginning of the row
- Display more information about the entry by clicking a link in the table.
- Sort the results by clicking the table headers in any column.
- Change the columns shown in the table by clicking the right arrow icon in the upper left corner of the table. In the dialog, check the box of the columns to be displayed.
- Search the table contents using the fields above the table and the "Search" button. See section 2.1.5 for more information.
- Change the number of entries displayed per page using the "Rows" drop-down menu above the table.
- Scroll through additional pages using the arrow buttons below the table or by entering a number in the "Page" field.
- Export table contents to an Excel table or in a tab-delimited format using the "Export" drop-down menu above the table. See section 2.1.6 for more information.

2.1.5. Searching in tables/result sets

Table contents can be searched. In this way, a search on a result set can be performed or refined.

1. Select the column in which to search from the drop-down menu above the table.
2. Enter the search term in the field next to the "Search" button.
3. Click the "+" (plus) button to add additional search terms and columns.
4. Click the "Search" button.
5. The search results will be displayed in a table.

2.1.6. Exporting

Exporting results from a table

Table contents can be exported to an Excel table or in tab-delimited format using the "Export" drop-down menu in the toolbar above the table, as shown in Figure 3.

- Select the rows to export by putting a check mark in the first column. (You can select and deselect all rows by clicking the check mark in the header row.)
- Select the export method ("Excel" or "Tab-delimited") in the "Export" drop-down menu above the table.
- A progress dialog will be displayed. For larger exports there is the option to put the export to the background. When the export is finished, you can get the exported file by clicking the "Get file" button.

The screenshot shows the BioXM Characterisations interface. At the top, there is a toolbar with buttons for Actions, Export, (0) Collect, and Admin. The main area is titled "Particle Characterisation" and contains a table of "Characterisation data". The table has columns for "Nominal size in dispersion [nm]", "Nominal size as text", "Minimal nominal size", "Maximal nominal size", "Shape", and "Crystallinity". A row is selected, showing "Nanoparticle" with a nominal size of 20.0 nm and a spherical shape. The "Export" menu is open, showing options for "Excel", "Tab delimited", and "Background exports".

Figure 3. Exporting - Select 1-n entries from the table by putting a check mark in the open box of the first column and select either "Excel" or "Tab delimited" format from the drop-down Export menu in the toolbar above the table.

Retrieving an export executed in the background

To view an export executed in the background, click the "Background exports" option in the "Export" drop-down menu above the table. A list of exports, which have been placed into the background, will be shown. Select the export you wish to retrieve.

2.1.7. Working with the Actions menu

Depending on the specific configuration some object types may be associated with specific actions. These may include calling sequence similarity searches from protein sequences or navigating from a specific NM to its associated toxicity measurements. If configured the actions are available from the toolbar "Actions" drop-down menu above the table.

1. Select the rows to perform the action on by checking the first column. (You can select and

deselect all rows by checking the respective box in the header row.)

2. Select the action to be performed (options depending on the specific configuration) in the "Actions" drop-down menu above the table.
3. Depending on the specific action further input may be necessary or progress dialogs may be displayed.

2.1.8. Working with panels

Reports may use multiple panels to structure a page, as shown in Figure 4. Every panel offers two interactions:

1. “-/+” icon – collapse/expand the panel to hide/access its content.
2. Double arrow icon – expand/collapse panel to/from full screen.

Entry	Toxicity	Name	ATC_Codes	ATC	C

Figure 4. Panels allow users to sub-structure report pages. Each panel can be opened/collapsed using the +/- icon in the top right corner. An open panel can be expanded to full screen using the double arrow icon in the top right corner.

2.1.9. Working with graphs

Access to integrated knowledge networks is often provided in graphical form, as shown in Figure 5. Every graph provides the following actions:

1. Paper sheet icon – display the graph objects as table report
2. Rhombus icon – zoom to fit the graph into the available window
3. Magnifier “+” icon – zoom in
4. Magnifier “-” icon – zoom out
5. Drop down list – select from predefined information overlays
6. Arrow icon – Export to external graph viewer

Clicking on an individual item (node or edge) in the graph will open a detailed report.

Figure 5. Graphs - the graph panel provides a visualisation of selected parts of the overall KB.

2.2. Data access using the GUI of the NanoCommons Knowledge Base

General Search

On the top menu bar the general search field can be used to query all information integrated into the NanoCommons KB and retrieve a list of any object matching the search term(s).

2.2.1. Data Access

The Data Access page provides access to NanoCommons content based on the different types of information accessible by individual buttons and described in detail below. The following Buttons are available (as shown in Figure 6), and described below in further detail:

- Particles
- Characterisations
- Toxicology
- Omics - described previously in Deliverable D5.2
- Parameters

Figure 6. Data Access page of the NanoCommons KB portal.

2.2.1.1. Particles

The “Particles” page provides two search options. “View all Particles” lists all NMs available in the NanoCommons KB. “View Particles with Data” searches for those NMs for which physicochemical characterisation and/or toxicology data is available, as shown in Figure 7.

Particles

Figure 7. Particles - the “Particles” page provides two specific searches available as linked pages by clicking on the corresponding Button.

View all Particles

Click the “View all Particles” button on the Particles page to display the list of all NMs currently available in the NanoCommons KB.

The results are displayed as a table, as shown in Figure 8 below. The table can be used as described in Section 2.1.4.

The columns are described below:

1. **ID** — the unique particle ID provided by the BioXM system upon registration of the NM in the NanoCommons KB (note that registration of a NM is a prerequisite to upload data regarding that NM);
2. **Chemical Elements** — the chemical element(s) constituting the NM
3. **Characterisation data** — if available, any associated physico-chemical characterisation measurements;
4. **Samples** – production batches of the NMs (e.g., lot numbers for commercial NMs);
5. **Aliquots** — any aliquots derived from the production batches of the NM and distributed for experimental measurements;
6. **All names** — names associated with the NM by different users/providers;
7. **Description** – production process notes;
8. **Ageing reaction** – if applicable, a description of the ageing reaction performed on the NM.

Particle General Information

ID	Chemical Elements	Characterisation data	Samples	Aliquots
NP00190	Ce	NP00190	SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-030314 SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-230114 SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-300114	SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-030314b SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-230114a SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-300114a SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-030314b SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-030314b SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-030314b SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-030314b SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-030314b SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-030314b SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-030314b SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-030314b SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-030314b SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-030314b SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-030314b SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-030314b SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-030314b SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-030314b

All names	Description	Aging reaction
Micron sized control;CeO2 bulk	< 5 micron (will also ball-mill to make smaller)	

NP00191	Ce	NP00191	JRC-CeO2-NM02101a002230 JRC-CeO2-NM211-1967	JRC-CeO2-NM211-2163a JRC-CeO2-NM211-2204a
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Figure 8. View all Particles - results table. Note, the red “-” icon in front of the first table row indicating expansion of columns initially hidden due to a small screen.

View all Particles with Data

Click the “View all Particles with Data” button on the Particles page to display the list of all NMs for which any experimental measurement data are currently available in the NanoCommons KB, i.e., for which experimental or computational data and metadata have been uploaded.

The results are displayed as a table as shown in Figure 9. The table can be used as described in Section 2.1.4.

The columns are described below:

1. **ID** — the unique particle ID provided upon registration of the NM in the NanoCommons KB;
2. **Chemical Elements** — the chemical element(s) constituting the NM;
3. **Characterisation data** — if available, any associated physicochemical characterisation measurements and the associated protocols and metadata;
4. **Toxicity data** – if available, any toxicity measurements generated for the NM;
5. **RNA-Seq** – if available, any RNA-seq transcriptomics measurements generated for the NM;
6. **Mass Spectrometry** – if available, any mass spectrometry (protein, metabolite) based measurements for the NM;
7. **Mesocosm** – if available, any complex environmental toxicology measurements for the NM.

Particles with Data

The screenshot shows a web interface for viewing particles. At the top, there is a search bar with the text "NP00190 OR NP00697" and buttons for "Search" and "Add". Below the search bar, it says "Selected items: 0" and "Show/Hide" and "Sort by" options. The main table has columns: ID, Chemical Elements, Characterisation data, Toxicity, RNA-Seq, Mass Spectrometry, and Mescocsm. Two rows are visible:

ID	Chemical Elements	Characterisation data	Toxicity	RNA-Seq	Mass Spectrometry	Mescocsm
<input type="checkbox"/> NP00190	Ce	NP00190	TOX000000000461 TOX000000000530 TOX000000000591 TOX000000000650 TOX000000000694 TOX000000000755 TOX000000000816 TOX000000000864 TOX000000000917 TOX000000000976 TOX000000000082			
<input type="checkbox"/> NP00697	Ag	NP00697				DS00000205_Stock dispersion_Rep1 DS00000206_Stock dispersion_Rep DS00000208_Stock dispersion_Rep1

Figure 9. View all Particles - results table. Note: the table has been filtered for two specific NM identifiers as described above.

Action to search for PhysChem/Tox Data associated with any selected NM

As described in Section 2.1.7, an action has been configured which allows to directly search for any available physico-chemical characterisation or toxicity measurements for NMs selected in any of the “Particle” results tables.

To this end, select the desired number of rows of the results table and select either “PhysChemData” or “ToxicologyData” from the “Actions” drop-down menu in the toolbar above the table, as shown in Figure 10. The resulting tables for the characterisation data and the toxicity data are described next.

The screenshot shows the "Particle General Information" interface. At the top, there is a search bar and buttons for "Search" and "Add". Below the search bar, it says "Selected items: 1" and "Show/Hide" and "Sort by" options. The main table has columns: ID, Chemical Elements, Characterisation data, Samples, Aliquots, and Further Information. Two rows are visible:

ID	Chemical Elements	Characterisation data	Samples	Aliquots	Further Information
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NP00190	Ce	NP00190	SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-030314 SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-230114 SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-300114	SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-030314b SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-230114a SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-300114a SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-030314b SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-030314b SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-030314b SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-030314b SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-030314b SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-030314b SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-030314b SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-030314b SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-030314b SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-030314b SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-030314b SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-030314b SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-030314b SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-030314b SIGMA-CeO2Bulk-5microns-030314b	Micron sized control;CeO2 bulk
<input type="checkbox"/> NP00191	Ce	NP00191	JRC-CeO2-NM02101a002230 JRC-CeO2-NM211-1967 JRC-CeO2-NM211-2005 JRC-CeO2-NM211-2014	JRC-CeO2-NM211-2163a JRC-CeO2-NM211-2204a JRC-CeO2-NM211-2204b JRC-CeO2-NM211-2204c	Cerium (IV) Oxide (precipitated, uncoated) NM-211;JRCNM02101a;Ce NM 211

Figure 10. Particle general information.

2.2.1.2. Characterisation data

This function searches and displays all physicochemical characterisation measurements available in the NanoCommons KB. The results will be displayed as a table as shown in Figure 11. The table can be used as described in section 2.1.4.

The columns are described below:

1. **ID** — the unique ID automatically generated by the BioXM system upon registration of a specific NM in the NanoCommons KB (a prerequisite for data upload and linking);
2. **Characterisation parameters** — the list of available characterisation parameters is dynamically presented in the report. Please refer to the Section 2.2.1.4 to get a specific list of available parameters.

Particle Characterisation

Characterisation data

Nanoparticle

Selected Items: 2

	Nominal size in dispersion [nm]	Nominal size as text	Minimal nominal size	Maximal nominal size	Shape	Crystallinity
Nanoparticle	-	-	-	-	-	-
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NP00193	20.0 nm				Spherical	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NP00194		Primary particle size ~5-10 nm	5	10	Spherical	
<input type="checkbox"/> NP00195		Primary particle size ~5-10 nm	5	10	Spherical	
<input type="checkbox"/> NP00196		Primary particle size ~5-10 nm	5	10	Spherical	

Figure 11. Characterisations – This section displays the physico-chemical characterisations available in the NanoCommons KB. Note the “+” Button at the beginning of each row to display further columns as described above. The number of columns is dynamically extended as further characterisation parameters become available.

Action “ToxicologyData”

As described above, an action has been configured which allows to directly search for any available toxicity measurements for NMs displayed in the “Particle Characterisation” table.

To this end, select the desired rows of the results table and select “ToxicologyData” from the “Actions” drop-down menu in the toolbar above the table (Figure 12).

The screenshot shows the 'Particle Characterisation' interface. At the top, there is a search bar with 'Nanoparticle' entered and a 'Search' button. Below the search bar, there is a table with the following data:

	Nominal size in dispersion [nm]	Nominal size as text	Minimal nominal size	Maximal nominal size	Shape	Crystallinity
NP00193	20.0 nm				Spherical	
NP00194		Primary particle size -5-10 nm	5	10	Spherical	

Figure 12. The resulting table of Particle Characterisation data.

2.2.1.3. Toxicology

The “Toxicology” page provides three search options as shown in Figure 13 and described below.

Toxicology

Figure 13. Toxicology - the “Toxicology” page provides three specific search options.

View Toxicity Data sets

This option lists all datasets which are available in the NanoCommons KB. This allows the identification of specific datasets of interest containing toxicity data.

The results are displayed as a table as shown in Figure 14. The table can be used as described in Section 2.1.4.

The available columns are:

1. **Data set** — the data set name as provided by the submitter.
2. **Data Set Type** – the type of submitted measurement e.g. NOAEL or single toxicity measurement. This column can be used for filtering with respect to specific dataset types.
3. **Tox Measurements** – number of the individual toxicity measurements submitted within the data set.
4. **N° Particles** – number of particles used to produce the toxicity measurements.

D4.6 Description of tools for automated data mining

5. **Provider** – institution providing the dataset and data owner.
6. **Country** – country the submitting institution or its department is located in.
7. **N^o Parameters** – number of parameters measured in the submitted dataset.

Toxicity Data sets

All toxicity data sets

Data Set Search

Selected Items: 0 Show/Hide Sort by

Data Set	Data Set Type	Tox. Measurements	No Particles	Provider	Country	No Parameters
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> JRC	Toxicity	260	24	JRC -JOINT RESEARCH CENTRE - EUROPEAN COMMISSION	Belgium	23
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> JRC_run19-21	Toxicity	540	52	JRC -JOINT RESEARCH CENTRE - EUROPEAN COMMISSION	Belgium	23
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> JRC_run22-24	Toxicity	210	19	JRC -JOINT RESEARCH CENTRE - EUROPEAN COMMISSION	Belgium	23
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> KIT_IH_A549	Toxicity	144	16	KARLSRUHER INSTITUT FUER TECHNOLOGIE	Germany	23
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> KIT_IH_HCT116	Toxicity	144	16	KARLSRUHER INSTITUT FUER TECHNOLOGIE	Germany	23

Figure 14. View Toxicity Data sets result table.

View Toxicity Measurements by Data sets

This option allows users to search by toxicity measurements based on (parts of) the name(s) of the datasets they were originally submitted in, as shown in Figure 15.

To perform a search:

1. Enter a sub-string of the name of the dataset of interest in the "Data set Name" search field
2. Click the "Search" button to perform the search.

Toxicity Data: Search by Data set

Toxicity data, search for data set

Data set Name

Figure 15. View Toxicity Measurements by Data sets - search form to retrieve all data sets matching the entered text as a substring somewhere in the data set name, alias or description.

The results will be displayed as a table as shown in Figure 16. The table can be used as described in section 2.1.4. The columns are:

1. **Measurement** – the unique ID assigned to the measurement during submission
2. **Description** – the description of the measurement as provided by the submitter
3. **Time** – duration of exposure to the nanomaterial, after which the measurement was taken

D4.6 Description of tools for automated data mining

4. **Dosis** [$\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$] – the nanomaterial concentration in micrograms per milliliter
5. **Dataset Name** – the data set name as provided by the submitter
6. **Dataset ID** – unique ID assigned to the data set during submission
7. **Dataset Description** – the description of the data set as provided by the submitter
8. **Dataset Synonyms** – other names assigned to the data set by the provider or other users
9. **Sample Aliquot name** – the name of the measured sample as provided by the submitter
10. **Sample Aliquot ID** – unique ID assigned to the sample during submission
11. **Sample Description** - the description of the sample as provided by the submitter
12. **Sample Time of Measurement** – the specific age of the sample before being used in the measurement
13. **Sample Ageing** – the method used to age the sample before exposing them to cells, organisms or performing the physicochemical measurements
14. **Particle** – see section 2.2.1.1.

The screenshot shows a web interface for searching toxicity data. At the top, there is a search bar with a dropdown menu set to 'Measurement'. Below the search bar, there is a table with columns for 'Measurement', 'Description', 'Time', 'Dosis [$\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$]', 'Dataset', and 'Sample'. The 'Sample' column is further divided into 'Aliquot ID', 'Description', 'Time of Measurement', 'Aging', and 'NanoParticle'. A dropdown menu is open over the 'Actions' column, showing 'PhysChemData' and 'ToxicologyData'. Below the table, there is a 'Particle' section with columns for 'Chemical Element', 'Aging reaction', 'All names', 'Designator', and 'NanoFASE name'.

Measurement	Description	Time	Dosis [$\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$]	Dataset		Sample			Aliquot ID	Description	Time of Measurement	Aging	NanoParticle
				ID	Dataset	Description	Synonyms	Aliquot name					
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TOX000000000197	24.0 h	0.5	JRC	DS00000003	JRC	JRC	JRC-CeO2-NM212-original_vial-a	AL000564				NP00192
Particle Chemical Element: Ce Aging reaction: Cerium (IV) Oxide (precipitated, uncoated) NM-212;JRCNM02102a;Ce NM 212 Designator: JRC NanoFASE name: JRC													
<input type="checkbox"/>	TOX000000000198	24.0 h	0.5	JRC	DS00000003	JRC	JRC	PROM-TiO2un-10nm-121113e	AL000122				NP00255
<input type="checkbox"/>	TOX000000000199	24.0 h	0.5	JRC	DS00000003	JRC	JRC	JRC-TiO2-NM103-original_vial-a	AL000567				NP00259

Figure 16. Toxicity Measurements by Data sets – The table of toxicity measurements belonging to the searched data sets. Note the Action menu allows retrieval of the associated Toxicity data.

Action “ToxicologyData”

As described in section 2.1.7, an action has been configured which allows users to directly search for any available toxicity measurements for NMs displayed in the “Particle Characterisation” table.

To this end, select the desired rows in the results table and select “ToxicologyData” from the “Actions” drop-down menu in the toolbar above the table.

The results will be displayed as a table. The table can be used as described in section 2.1.4.

The columns are described below:

1. **Measurement** — the unique ID assigned to the measurement during submission
2. **Toxicity parameters** — the list of available characterisation parameters is dynamically presented in the report. Please refer to section 2.2.1.4 to get a specific list of available parameters.

2.2.1.4. Parameters

Searches for all parameters measured in any of the available measurements can be performed.

Click the “Parameters” button on the Data Access page to display the list of parameters currently available in the NanoCommons KB. The result lists all parameters in tabular form as per Figure 17.

The columns are described below:

1. **ID** – unique ID generated during submission of the parameter
2. **Parameter** – name of the parameter provided by the submitter
3. **Synonyms** – any synonyms provided for a specific parameter by the submitter or other users
4. **Description** – description of the parameter provided by the submitter or other users
5. **Data type** – data type of the parameter e.g. numeric or text
6. **Comment** – any comments provided
7. **eNM** – links to eNanoMapper ontology entries which define the parameter
8. **Ontology links** – links to ontology entries (eNanoMapper or other) which define the parameter
9. **Number of experiments** – the number of measurements a parameter has been measured in.

Parameters

Search Parameters by ID or Name			
<input type="text" value="ID"/>	<input type="text" value="*0654 OR *0655"/>	<input type="button" value="Search"/>	<input type="button" value="+ Add"/>
Selected items: 0		Show/Hide	Sorted by Parameter
ID	Parameter	Synonyms	
<input type="checkbox"/>	VA00000654	AB_100_AVG	AB_100_AVG
Description AB_100_AVG, Alamar Blue toxicity test, percentage value vs reference control of each experiment, average value among replicates on same plate			
Data type numeric			
Comment			
eNM ENM:8000224 Alamar Blue assay			
Ontology links ENM:8000224 Alamar Blue assay			
Number of experiments 712			
<input type="checkbox"/>	VA00000655	AB_100_MED	AB_100_MED

Figure 17. Parameters – result table providing detailed information about the measurement parameters available from the NanoCommons KB.

3. Data retrieval from NanoCommons KB to the Jaqpot modelling environment

In this section we present the tools that have been developed to automatically retrieve data from the NanoCommons KB and make them available to the Jaqpot modelling environment for further processing and analysis. More specifically, we present a complete workflow, implemented through a Jupyter notebook in Python.

The workflow begins with retrieving physicochemical characterisation and biological data from the NanoCommons KB for 15 metal oxide NMs of various shapes, both coated and uncoated. The workflow continues with data preprocessing, building a predictive model for predicting one biological endpoint (namely the Viable Cell Count of A549 adenocarcinomic human alveolar basal epithelial cells, for a dose of 39.1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ after 24 hours of exposure) and deploying the model as a web service through the Jaqpot modelling platform developed by NTUA.

The technical details on establishing the communication between the NanoCommons KB and Jaqpot through APIs have been described in detail in Deliverable D4.2. The complete python notebook is available under GNU General Public License at:

<https://github.com/NanoCommons/notebooks/blob/master/D4.6Deliverables/JaqpotNanoCommonsKB.ipynb>.

We will demonstrate data retrieval from the NanoCommons KB via the APIs, building a model on the data using NanoCommons computational services and making the model and the underpinning dataset available in Jaqpot 5 within the NanoCommons infrastructure. The python calls made to the BIOMAX services will be explained along with the commands used for data processing to make it ready for use in modelling. Please note that while the output returned by some commands has to be extensive, to serve checking and debugging, for this presentation we will only present the lines that are relevant for this short introduction. After being made available on Jaqpot, the model can be used by the community to support decision making.

3.1. Initial steps

3.1.1. Import/install necessary packages for communication with NanoCommons KB

Initially, the user needs to add functionality to the Jupyter notebook by installing the required packages. Here, we only install the packages necessary for communication and basic data handling. The additional packages will be presented in the modelling step:

```
import sys
pip install requests
pip install pandas
import getpass
import requests
import sys
import http.client as http_client
```

```
import logging
import json
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
```

3.1.2. Setting up a communication session with the NanoCommons KB

In order to be able to communicate with the NanoCommons KB, the first step is to establish a connection. Since access to the NanoCommons KB is restricted to registered users, access is only possible with a username and a password (see section 2.1.1 on how an account can be obtained via the GUI of the knowledge platform). Depending on the environment the service is used in, it might also be necessary to define proxies, but this was not the case here.

```
user = "Hackathon"
pw = getpass.getpass("Login password for user '{}': ".format(user))
url = "https://ssl.biomax.de/nanocommons_old/bioxm/rest/api"

proxies = { #'https': 'server:8080' }
```

These credentials are posted using the `requests.get` command:

```
print("Opening session...")
response = requests.get(
url + "/createUserSessionSimple?name={}&password={}".format(user, pw),
proxies=proxies)
```

```
Login password for user 'Hackathon': .....
Opening session...
```

With a valid username and password the user is connected, resulting to an “**Opened session**” message accompanied with the ID of the session. In case of failure, the user is provided with a “**Failed to open session:**” message with a short description of the problem encountered.

```
session_id = ""
if response.status_code == 200:
    session_id = response.text
    print("Opened session " + session_id)
else:
    print("Failed to open session: " + str(response.text))
sys.exit(1)
```

```
Opened session 4450d25f8a224128b3d19991b35d25e6edd2bc62
```

```
...
```

```
Closed session.
```

3.2. Queries and data retrieval from the NanoCommons KB

3.2.1. Retrieving Characterisation data from the NanoCommons KB

After establishing a connection, requests can be made by specifying queries to the KB, which are customisable following a simple syntax. This will provide us with the characterisation section of the dataset. The toxicity data will be retrieved in a subsequent step.

- the **queryName** variable, which defines the dataset that will be retrieved. Here a specific predefined query is used, which retrieves characterisation data for the 15 metal oxide NMs of various shapes, both coated and uncoated that are of interest.
- the **viewName** variable, which defines a specific view for the dataset.

```
request_data= """
{
  "SearchResultWithReportsRequest":
  {
    "firstIndex": 0,
    "maxCount": 100,
    "local": False,
    "viewName": "ivan",
    "query": {
      "queryName": "ivan"
    }
  }
}
"""
```

As here we were only describing the request data but the actual request is made in the next step, no output was produced. After the query with its relevant parameters has been defined locally in the notebook (stored in the *request_data* variable), we also define other parameters, with the most important one given in the first line, wherein headers we define the content type to be JSON (stored in the *headers* variable):

```
try:
    headers = {'Content-type': 'application/json'}
    http_client.HTTPConnection.debuglevel = 1
    logging.basicConfig()
    logging.getLogger().setLevel(logging.DEBUG)
    requests_log = logging.getLogger("requests.packages.urllib3")
    requests_log.setLevel(logging.DEBUG)
    requests_log.propagate = True
```

The request with its parameters is sent to the NanoCommons KB with the following *requests.post* command:

```
response = requests.post(url +
```

```
"/getSearchResultWithReports?userSessionId=" + session_id,
data=request_data,headers=headers, proxies=proxies)
```

We print the status of the request made with the code we received. Afterwards, for successful requests, marked with the status code 200, the data from the NanoCommons KB in *response.text* is stored into the *json_data2* variable using the *json.loads* command that retrieves a JSON structure.

```
print("Status: " + str(response.status_code))

if (response.status_code == 200):
    json_data2 = json.loads(response.text)

else:
    print("ERROR:")
    print(response.text)
```

As this interaction is finished, we end the session and return a message notifying the user if the session has been closed successfully.

```
finally:
    response = requests.get(url + "/destroyUserSession?userSessionId=" +
session_id, proxies=proxies)
    if (response.status_code == 200):
        print("\nClosed session.")
    else:
        print("\nError: Failed to close session " + session_id)
```

The *json_data2* contains the JSON response returned from the KB. The first lines are shown below.

```
{'SearchResultWithReports': {'totalCount': 16,
'objectReports': [{'objectURL': 'Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00262',
'attributes': [{'name': 'Particle',
'type': 'object',
'error': False,
'forbidden': False,
'values': 'NP00262'}],
{'name': '..Type',
'type': 'report',
'error': False,
'forbidden': False,
'nestedReports': {'objectURL':
...

```

Within the schema of the JSON, we notice the *'SearchResultWithReports'* object that contains the *'objectReports'* object, which in turn contains, among others, arrays for each *'objectURL'*. In the *'objectURL'* field we find the information for the substance names, which we will insert into the *Id*

column of the *data_dict* variable. Using the `append` command we add to the *Id* column of the *data_dict* variable the *objectURL* and the *attributes* and *values* to the key of the *data_dict*. Finally the *data_dict* variable is converted to a Pandas Dataframe, stored as a new variable, *df*, which we print.

```

data_dict = {}
data_dict['Id'] = []
for dato in json_data2['SearchResultWithReports']['objectReports']:
    for atr in dato['attributes']:
        data_dict[atr['name']] = []
for dato in json_data2['SearchResultWithReports']['objectReports']:
    data_dict['Id'].append(dato["objectURL"])
    for key, value in data_dict.items():
        for atr in dato['attributes']:
            if atr['name'] == key:
                try:
                    nr = atr['nestedReports']
                    data_dict[key].append(nr['attributes']['values'])
                except KeyError:
                    data_dict[key].append(None)
                continue

df = pd.DataFrame(data_dict)
print(df)

```

	Id	Particle	..Type	..Coating \
0	Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00262	None	Si	aminoacid
1	Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00266	None	Si	aminoalkyl
2	Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00269	None	Si	aminoacid
3	Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00255	None	Ti	uncoated
4	Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00256	None	Ti	PVP
5	Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00257	None	Ti	F127
6	Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00258	None	Ti	AA4040
7	Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00259	None	Ti	uncoated
8	Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00260	None	Ti	uncoated
9	Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00254	None	Ti	uncoated
10	Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00193	None	Ce	uncoated
11	Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00192	None	Ce	uncoated
12	Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00282	None	Zn	uncoated
13	Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00283	None	Zn	triethoxycaprilysilane
14	Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00214a	None	Ag	uncoated
15	Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00214b	None	Ag	uncoated

	..Type of Coating	..Surface Modification	..Shape \
0	neutral	None	Spherical
1	positive	None	Spherical
2	negative	None	Spherical
3	uncoated	None	Spherical

D4.6 Description of tools for automated data mining

4	neutral		None	Square/Spherical/Rods
5	neutral		None	Square
6	neutral		None	Square
7	uncoated	hydrophobic	rutile	Nanorods
8	uncoated	hydrophilic	rutile	Nanorods
9	uncoated		None	Spherical/ Square
10	uncoated		None	Spherical
11	uncoated		None	Cubic
12	uncoated		None	Various shapes
13	neutral		None	Various Shapes
14	uncoated		None	Spherical
15	uncoated		None	Spherical

	_.Nominal Size (nm)	_.DLS (nm)	_.DLS SD (nm)	...	_.TEM Shortest (nm) \
0	20	28.90	25.19000	...	NaN
1	20	23.48	0.08185	...	NaN
2	20	25.24	0.77130	...	NaN
3	10	1325.00	74.47000	...	8.00
4	10	3185.00	181.60000	...	11.86
5	10	4391.00	287.40000	...	13.40
6	10	3109.00	140.50000	...	NaN
7	20	1609.00	917.80000	...	18.10
8	20	403.00	51.32000	...	25.40
9	70	172.40	1.21200	...	NaN
10	20	269.50	8.97900	...	NaN
11	33	257.70	14.32000	...	NaN
12	150	411.80	7.11200	...	NaN
13	140	NaN	NaN	...	NaN
14	15	27.36	0.11480	...	NaN
15	15	27.36	0.11480	...	NaN

	_.TEM Shortest SD (nm)	_.TEM Longest (nm)	_.TEM Longest SD (nm) \
0	NaN	NaN	NaN
1	NaN	NaN	NaN
2	NaN	NaN	NaN
3	2.90	8.99	2.32
4	3.27	5.10	3.30
5	10.40	5.10	3.20
6	NaN	13.90	9.90
7	6.70	40.70	14.80
8	8.40	42.50	15.30
9	NaN	27.80	9.20
10	NaN	NaN	NaN
11	NaN	NaN	NaN
12	NaN	87.70	56.60
13	NaN	NaN	NaN
14	NaN	NaN	NaN
15	NaN	NaN	NaN

	_.STEM (nm)	_.STEM SD (nm)	_.BET (m ² /g)	_.BET SD(m ² /g) \
0	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
1	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
2	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
3	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

D4.6 Description of tools for automated data mining

4	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
5	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
6	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
7	NaN	NaN	52.500	0.30
8	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
9	NaN	NaN	61.200	0.70
10	5.2	1.3	NaN	NaN
11	17.1	10.9	28.790	0.22
12	NaN	NaN	12.131	NaN
13	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
14	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
15	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	_.Energy Band Gap (eV)	_.Geometric Surface Area (nm ²)
0	NaN	1206.874234
1	NaN	1206.874234
2	NaN	1206.874234
3	NaN	180.271745
4	NaN	224.541375
5	NaN	325.380000
6	NaN	1159.260000
7	NaN	2828.925645
8	NaN	4404.764228
9	NaN	3532.494233
10	3.221	84.948665
11	2.685	1754.460000
12	2.236	35155.320080
13	NaN	6891.629050
14	2.506	1398.217746
15	2.506	1398.217746

[16 rows x 28 columns]

3.2.2. Retrieving the toxicity data from the NanoCommons KB

In the same spirit as with the characterisation data, the user invokes a query to the KB in order to retrieve the toxicity data. As shown with the characterisation data in Section 3.2.1, the query for the toxicity data is defined by:

- the **queryName** variable

This defines the dataset that will be retrieved. Here we provide the value "*Experiment - Toxicity - KIT IH A549*", which corresponds to experiments on A549 adenocarcinomic human alveolar basal epithelial cells performed by KIT, the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, using the NMs of interest defined in Section 3.2.1.

- the **viewName** variable

This defines a specific view for the dataset, here with the value "*Experiment - Toxicity by aliquot*".

```
request_data=
```

```
''''
```

```

{
  "SearchResultWithReportsRequest":
  {
    "firstIndex": 0,
    "maxCount": 100,
    "local": True,
    "viewName": "Experiment - Toxicity by aliquot",
    "query": {
      "queryName": "Experiment - Toxicity - KIT IH A549"
    }
  }
}
"""

```

After specifying the request parameters, we make the request and if received successfully, we store the data from the response variable and close the session.

```

try:
    headers = {'Content-type': 'application/json'}
    http_client.HTTPConnection.debuglevel = 1
    logging.basicConfig()
    logging.getLogger().setLevel(logging.DEBUG)
    requests_log = logging.getLogger("requests.packages.urllib3")
    requests_log.setLevel(logging.DEBUG)
    requests_log.propagate = True

    response = requests.post(url +
"/getSearchResultWithReports?userSessionId=" + session_id, data=request_data,
headers=headers, proxies=proxies)
    print("Status: " + str(response.status_code))

    if (response.status_code == 200):
        json_data2 = json.loads(response.text)
    else:
        print("ERROR:")
        print(response.text)

finally:
    response = requests.get(url + "/destroyUserSession?userSessionId=" +
session_id, proxies=proxies)
    if (response.status_code == 200):
        print("\nClosed session.")
    else:
        print("\nError: Failed to close session " + session_id)

```

Same as above, we store the data from *response.text* into the *json_data2* variable using the *json.loads* command that retrieves the JSON structure sent by the NanoCommons KB. As with the characterisation data, using the *append* command we add to the *Id* column of the *data_dictTox* variable the *objectURL* and the *attributes* and *values* to the key of the *data_dictTox* variable.

```

data_dictTox = {}
data_dictTox['Id'] = []
for dato in json_data2['SearchResultWithReports']['objectReports']:
    for atr in dato['attributes']:
        data_dictTox[atr['name']] = []
for dato in json_data2['SearchResultWithReports']['objectReports']:
    data_dictTox['Id'].append(dato["objectURL"])
    for key, value in data_dictTox.items():
        for atr in dato['attributes']:
            if atr['name'] == key:
                try:
                    nr = atr['nestedReports']
                    data_dictTox[key].append(nr['attributes'])
                except KeyError:
                    data_dictTox[key].append(None)
                    continue

```

Finally, the *data_dict* variable is converted to a pandas DataFrame, stored in the variable *dfTox*. The values of the variable are not printed here because the results were extensive and the reader is referenced to the jupyter notebook for the full display of the DataFrame.

```
dfTox = pd.DataFrame(data_dictTox)
```

3.3. Handling the data for modelling

3.3.1. Import/install necessary packages for preprocessing, modelling and uploading to Jaqpot

Now the user needs to import or install the software packages that are required for the next steps, namely:

- preprocessing the dataset in order to make it suitable for the construction of mathematical models

```

pip install sklearn
pip install matplotlib
from sklearn import preprocessing
from sklearn import preprocessing
from sklearn import utils

```

- building a model locally and assessing its performance

```

from sklearn.linear_model import LogisticRegression
from sklearn.linear_model import LogisticRegressionCV
from sklearn import metrics
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from sklearn import svm, datasets

```

D4.6 Description of tools for automated data mining

```

from sklearn.metrics import confusion_matrix
from sklearn.utils.multiclass import unique_labels

```

- uploading the model to Jaqpot and making it available as a web service using the Jaqpot python library extended as part of the NanoCommons project.

```

pip install jaqpotpy
from jaqpotpy import Jaqpot

```

3.3.2. Preprocessing Characterisation data for use in modelling

After storing the characterisation data in a separate variable, we remove the variables that do not contain values for all NMs. We also remove the “Id” and “Particle” columns that will not be used as inputs.

```

Xall_BIO=df
Xall_BIO=Xall_BIO.drop(['_DLS SD (nm)', '_PDI SD', '_Zeta SD (mV)', '_Electrophoretic mobility SD (µmcm/Vs)', '_TEM (nm)', '_TEM SD (nm)', '_TEM Shortest (nm)', '_TEM Shortest SD (nm)', '_TEM Longest (nm)', '_TEM Longest SD (nm)', '_STEM (nm)', '_STEM SD (nm)', '_BET (m^2/g)', '_BET SD(m^2/g)', '_Energy Band Gap (eV)'],axis=1)
Xall_BIO=Xall_BIO.drop(Xall_BIO.index[[13]])
Xall_BIO=Xall_BIO.drop(['Id', 'Particle'],axis=1)

```

After removing some columns, the variable has to be restructured by modifying its index. We print the results to see how the input variable looks.

```

Xall_BIO.index=range(len(Xall_BIO))
Xall_BIO

```

	..Type	..Coating	..Type of Coating	..Surface Modification	..Shape	..Nominal Size (nm)	..DLS (nm)	..PDI	..Zeta (mV)	..Electrophoretic mobility (µmcm/Vs)	..Geometric Surface Area (nm ²)
0	Si	aminoacid	neutral	None	Spherical	20	28.90	0.110	-21.80	0.0879	1206.874234
1	Si	aminoalkyl	positive	None	Spherical	20	23.48	0.172	25.90	2.0300	1206.874234
2	Si	aminoacid	negative	None	Spherical	20	25.24	0.174	-31.70	-2.4840	1206.874234
3	Ti	uncoated	uncoated	None	Spherical	10	1325.00	0.277	20.50	1.6050	180.271745
4	Ti	PVP	neutral	None	Square/Spherical/Rods	10	3185.00	0.240	17.30	1.3610	224.541375
5	Ti	F127	neutral	None	Square	10	4391.00	0.172	5.30	0.4158	325.380000
6	Ti	AA4040	neutral	None	Square	10	3109.00	0.177	17.10	1.3440	1159.260000
7	Ti	uncoated	uncoated	hydrophobic rutile	Nanorods	20	1609.00	0.895	23.00	1.8040	2828.925645
8	Ti	uncoated	uncoated	hydrophilic rutile	Nanorods	20	403.00	0.810	25.30	1.9810	4404.764228
9	Ti	uncoated	uncoated	None	Spherical/ Square	70	172.40	0.183	41.00	3.2170	3532.494233
10	Ce	uncoated	uncoated	None	Spherical	20	269.50	0.291	32.90	2.3810	84.948665
11	Ce	uncoated	uncoated	None	Cubic	33	257.70	0.510	56.40	4.0850	1754.460000
12	Zn	uncoated	uncoated	None	Various shapes	150	411.80	0.239	-20.30	-1.5940	35155.320080
13	Ag	uncoated	uncoated	None	Spherical	15	27.36	0.471	-5.52	-0.3994	1398.217746
14	Ag	uncoated	uncoated	None	Spherical	15	27.36	0.471	-5.52	-0.3994	1398.217746

Afterwards, variables that are categorical (instead of numbers, their values are “positive” / “negative”

D4.6 Description of tools for automated data mining

etc.) will be transformed so that the categories they describe are represented by numerical values and thus can be used by common algorithms. For that purpose, we employ the LabelEncoder function: each variable first needs to be fitted to the data, which will involve first identifying the different values present in each variable and subsequently transforming the data so that each categorical value is substituted with a numerical value. The result of this will be to have all the information on the differences among each instance of variable but stored in numerical values that are much easier to handle. We do this for “..Type”, “..Coating”, “..Type of Coating”, “..Shape”, “..Surface Modification” sequentially.

```

LE = preprocessing.LabelEncoder()
LE.fit(Xall_BIO['..Type'])
Xall_BIO['..Type']= LE.transform(Xall_BIO['..Type'])

LE.fit(Xall_BIO['..Coating'])
Xall_BIO['..Coating']= LE.transform(Xall_BIO['..Coating'])

LE.fit(Xall_BIO['..Type of Coating'])
Xall_BIO['..Type of Coating']= LE.transform(Xall_BIO['..Type of Coating'])

LE.fit(Xall_BIO['..Shape'])
Xall_BIO['..Shape']= LE.transform(Xall_BIO['..Shape'])

Xall_BIO['..Surface Modification']=Xall_BIO['..Surface Modification'].astype(str)
LE.fit(Xall_BIO['..Surface Modification'])
Xall_BIO['..Surface Modification']= LE.transform(Xall_BIO['..Surface Modification'])

```

After processing, the values of the independent variables are all numerical, without any missing values.

Xall_BIO												
	..Type	..Coating	..Type of Coating	..Surface Modification	..Shape	..Nominal Size (nm)	..DLS (nm)	..PDI	..Zeta (mV)	..Electrophoretic mobility (µmcm/Vs)	..Geometric Surface Area (nm ²)	
0	2	3	1	0	2	20	28.90	0.110	-21.80	0.0879	1206.874234	
1	2	4	2	0	2	20	23.48	0.172	25.90	2.0300	1206.874234	
2	2	3	0	0	2	20	25.24	0.174	-31.70	-2.4840	1206.874234	
3	3	5	3	0	2	10	1325.00	0.277	20.50	1.6050	180.271745	
4	3	2	1	0	5	10	3185.00	0.240	17.30	1.3610	224.541375	
5	3	1	1	0	4	10	4391.00	0.172	5.30	0.4158	325.380000	
6	3	0	1	0	4	10	3109.00	0.177	17.10	1.3440	1159.260000	
7	3	5	3	2	1	20	1609.00	0.895	23.00	1.8040	2828.925645	
8	3	5	3	1	1	20	403.00	0.810	25.30	1.9810	4404.764228	
9	3	5	3	0	3	70	172.40	0.183	41.00	3.2170	3532.494233	
10	1	5	3	0	2	20	269.50	0.291	32.90	2.3810	84.948665	
11	1	5	3	0	0	33	257.70	0.510	56.40	4.0850	1754.460000	
12	4	5	3	0	6	150	411.80	0.239	-20.30	-1.5940	35155.320080	
13	0	5	3	0	2	15	27.36	0.471	-5.52	-0.3994	1398.217746	
14	0	5	3	0	2	15	27.36	0.471	-5.52	-0.3994	1398.217746	

3.3.3. Isolating the toxicity endpoint from the toxicity dataset

As the dataset contains multiple toxicity endpoints, it is necessary to extract the two essential variables from this dataset:

Firstly, the names of the compounds studied. These are part of the characterisation data as well, but they need to be retained in the toxicity dataset for cross-referencing the values.

```
dfToxNames=dfTox['_Particle']
CompoundNames={}
coumpountDict = {}
for compound in range(1,len(dfToxNames)):
    coumpountDict[compound] = dfToxNames[compound][0]['values']
CompoundNames['particle'] = coumpountDict
print(CompoundNames)
```

```
{'particle': {1: 'NP00375', 2: 'NP00262', 3: 'NP00266', 4: 'NP00269', 5:
'NP00255', 6: 'NP00256', 7: 'NP00257', 8: 'NP00258', 9: 'NP00259', 10:
'NP00260', 11: 'NP00254', 12: 'NP00193', 13: 'NP00192', 14: 'NP00282', 15:
'NP00283', 16: 'NP00214', 17: 'NP00214'}}
```

Secondly, the values for the toxicity endpoint(s) chosen for analysis, here “[_Toxicity.A549_Dose_39.1_IH](#)”, representing the Viable Cell Count of A549 adenocarcinomic human alveolar basal epithelial cells, following exposure to a dose of 39.1 µg/mL for 24 hours. We take the values from the dfTox variable and store them into a new variable, ViableCellCount.

```
dfTox2=dfTox['_Toxicity.A549_Dose_39.1_IH']
ViableCellCount={}
i=0
for compound in range(len(dfTox2)):
    df3=dfTox2[compound]
    df5=pd.DataFrame(df3, columns=['name', 'values'])
    ViableCellCount[compound]=df5.iloc[0]['values']
ViableCellCount
```

```
{0: nan,
1: nan,
2: 1.422835941,
3: -0.401260535,
4: 2.434066141,
5: -0.040606937,
6: 0.084394911,
7: 0.057642569,
8: 0.284920008,
9: -0.450941764,
```

```

10: 0.525510532,
11: -0.213755604,
12: 0.247470485,
13: 0.818199323,
14: -7.30424163,
15: -9.238114492,
16: -16.06765605,
17: -16.06765605}

```

At this point we have only transferred the values for the viable cell count, but we also need to have the respective particle name and proper “names” for the columns of the variables we will use.

For that purpose, we construct the `ViableCellCountdf` pandas DataFrame¹ so that it contains the values of the `ViableCellCount` variable with the heading “`ViableCellCount`” and the `dfNames` pandas DataFrame object, so that we get the names of the compounds in the dataset. Finally, we join them using the `pd.concat` command into one variable, `hackathonToxdata2`.

```

dictF = {}
dictF['ViableCellCount']=ViableCellCount
ViableCellCountdf = pd.DataFrame.from_dict(dictF)
dfNames = pd.DataFrame.from_dict(CompoundNames)
hackathonToxdata2 = pd.concat([dfNames, ViableCellCountdf], axis=1)
print(hackathonToxdata2)

```

	particle	ViableCellCount
0	NaN	NaN
1	NP00375	NaN
2	NP00262	1.422836
3	NP00266	-0.401261
4	NP00269	2.434066
5	NP00255	-0.040607
6	NP00256	0.084395
7	NP00257	0.057643
8	NP00258	0.284920
9	NP00259	-0.450942
10	NP00260	0.525511
11	NP00254	-0.213756
12	NP00193	0.247470
13	NP00192	0.818199

¹ <https://pandas.pydata.org/pandas-docs/stable/reference/api/pandas.DataFrame.html>

D4.6 Description of tools for automated data mining

14	NP00282	-7.304242
15	NP00283	-9.238114
16	NP00214	-16.067656
17	NP00214	-16.067656

Now the user needs to have the dependent variable values of the model as a separate variable, Yall. This must contain only data points that can be used for modelling. Since the two top rows do not contain values in both columns they will be removed.

```

hackathonToxdata2=hackathonToxdata2.drop(hackathonToxdata2.index[[0,1]])
hackathonToxdata2.index=range(len(hackathonToxdata2))
Yall=hackathonToxdata2['ViableCellCount']
Yall=Yall.drop(Yall.index[[13]])
Yall.index=range(len(Yall))
Yall
  
```

0	1.422836
1	-0.401261
2	2.434066
3	-0.040607
4	0.084395
5	0.057643
6	0.284920
7	-0.450942
8	0.525511
9	-0.213756
10	0.247470
11	0.818199
12	-7.304242
13	-16.067656
14	-16.067656

Name: ViableCellCount, dtype: float64

3.3.4. Preprocessing toxicity data for use as modelling endpoint values

The toxicity data will be transformed into binned values to be used in classification. As the Viable Cells Count values are continuous, we will employ the `pd.cut` function on the Yall variable to bin values into discrete intervals. We will define the bin edges with non-uniform width, specifying them in an accompanying variable, [-16.086,-1.266,0,2.435]. After that, we print the type of the new variable just created, YallBins and also retrieve the 4 categories where all Viable Cells Count values from Yall fall into:

```
YallBins=pd.cut(Yall, [-16.086, -1.266, 0, 2.435])
YallBins.dtypes
```

```
CategoricalDtype(categories=[(-16.086, -1.266], (-1.266, 0.0], (0.0, 2.435]],
                      ordered=True)
```

Printing the YallBins shows us in which bin each respective data point from Yall is categorised:

```
YallBins
0          (0.0, 2.435]
1        (-1.266, 0.0]
2          (0.0, 2.435]
3        (-1.266, 0.0]
4          (0.0, 2.435]
5          (0.0, 2.435]
6          (0.0, 2.435]
7        (-1.266, 0.0]
8          (0.0, 2.435]
9        (-1.266, 0.0]
10         (0.0, 2.435]
11         (0.0, 2.435]
12        (-16.086, -1.266]
13        (-16.086, -1.266]
14        (-16.086, -1.266]
Name:          ViableCellCount,      dtype:      category
Categories (3, interval[float64]): [(-16.086, -1.266] < (-1.266, 0.0] < (0.0, 2.435]]
```

We encode the ViableCellCount bins from YallBins as integers using the LabelEncoder function once more. The integers showing the bins of Yallbins are stored in the training_scores_encoded variable, which we print in order to inspect its values:

```
training_scores_Y=YallBins
lab_enc = preprocessing.LabelEncoder()
training_scores_encoded = lab_enc.fit_transform(training_scores_Y)

print(training_scores_encoded)
[2 1 2 1 2 2 2 1 2 1 2 2 0 0 0]
```

The training_scores_encoded variable is now a numpy array, which needs to be converted to a pandas DataFrame in order to be used later. Firstly, we employ the np.ravel function to return a contiguous flattened array from the training_scores_encoded variable, which we print, and then from it produce the training_scores_encodedPD variable using the pd.Series function to get pandas Series, which are one-dimensional labeled arrays capable of holding any data type. We print training_scores_encodedPD to see the difference from the initial training_scores_encoded variable.

```
print("NumPy array:")
```

```
training_scores_encoded=np.ravel(training_scores_encoded)
print(training_scores_encoded)
training_scores_encodedPD = pd.Series(training_scores_encoded)
print("Converted Pandas series:")
print(training_scores_encodedPD)
```

NumPy array:

```
[2 1 2 1 2 2 2 1 2 1 2 2 0 0 0]
```

Converted Pandas series:

```
0    2
1    1
2    2
3    1
4    2
5    2
6    2
7    1
8    2
9    1
10   2
11   2
12   0
13   0
14   0
```

dtype: int64

We employ the `.to_frame` function on the `training_scores_encodedPD` variable in order to convert its type from Series to DataFrame and then name it's one column '`ViableCellBins`'. Afterwards, we use the `pd.DataFrame` function to convert `training_scores_encodedPD` to a DataFrame.

```
training_scores_encodedPD=training_scores_encodedPD.to_frame(name=None)
training_scores_encodedPD.columns=['ViableCellBins']
training_scores_encodedPD= pd.DataFrame(training_scores_encodedPD)
training_scores_encodedPD
```

ViableCellBins	
0	2
1	1
2	2
3	1
4	2
5	2
6	2
7	1
8	2
9	1
10	2
11	2
12	0
13	0
14	0

3.4. Model development and validation

At this point, we will generate a local model employing the `LogisticRegressionCV` function for Logistic Regression classification. The model will produce predictions for the viable cell count, as expressed in bins in the `training_scores_encodedPD` variable. This will be the dependent variable (endpoint). As independent variables, the model will use the physicochemical characterisation data stored in the `Xall_BIO` variable.

Firstly, we fit the data using `.fit` and the independent variables and the endpoint as arguments, producing a model stored with its attributes in the `clf` dataframe. Using `clf.predict`, the model in `clf` can be used to generate predictions from the data in `Xall_BIO`.

```
clf = LogisticRegressionCV(cv=8,  
random_state=0,multi_class='auto').fit(Xall_BIO,training_scores_encodedPD)  
  
clf.predict(Xall_BIO)
```

In order to have a first assessment of model performance, we execute the following command, where the predictions of the model in `clf` are scored against the actual output of the function, `training_scores_encodedPD`.

```
clf.score(Xall_BIO, training_scores_encodedPD)
```

0.8

The following block of code will be used in the next step to plot the confusion matrices². It defines the python function that will be used in the next step so it does not produce results as yet.

```
def plot_confusion_matrix(y_true, y_pred, classes,
                          normalize=False,
                          title=None,
                          cmap=plt.cm.Blues):
    """
    This function prints and plots the confusion matrix.
    Normalization can be applied by setting `normalize=True`.
    """
    if not title:
        if normalize:
            title = 'Normalized confusion matrix'
        else:
            title = 'Confusion matrix, without normalization'

    # Compute confusion matrix
    cm = confusion_matrix(y_true, y_pred)
    # Only use the labels that appear in the data
    classes = Ynames
    if normalize:
        cm = cm.astype('float') / cm.sum(axis=1)[:, np.newaxis]
        print("Normalized confusion matrix")
    else:
        print('Confusion matrix, without normalization')

    print(cm)

    fig, ax = plt.subplots()
    im = ax.imshow(cm, interpolation='nearest', cmap=cmap)
    ax.figure.colorbar(im, ax=ax)
    # We want to show all ticks...
    ax.set(xticks=np.arange(cm.shape[1]),
          yticks=np.arange(cm.shape[0]),
          # ... and label them with the respective list entries
          xticklabels=classes, yticklabels=classes,
          title=title,
          ylabel='True label',
          xlabel='Predicted label')

    # Rotate the tick labels and set their alignment.
    plt.setp(ax.get_xticklabels(), rotation=45, ha="right",
             rotation_mode="anchor")

    # Loop over data dimensions and create text annotations.
    fmt = '.2f' if normalize else 'd'
```

² https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/model_evaluation.html#confusion-matrix

```

thresh          =          cm.max()          /          2.
for              i          in          range(cm.shape[0]):
    for          j          in          range(cm.shape[1]):
        ax.text(j,          i,          format(cm[i,          j],          fmt),
                ha="center",          va="center",
                color="white" if cm[i, j] > thresh else "black")
Figure.tight_layout()
return ax

```

We apply the model to the input data and generate predictions that we store in the *y_pred_test* variable. As the dataset is small and the aim of this presentation is focused on demonstrating the use of the tools, we use the same dataset to train and test the model. Here we present the code with general naming, so that it will be easier to reuse in other examples. Therefore we set the endpoint variable equal to the *training_scores_encodedPD* used in the training.

```

y_pred_test=clf.predict(Xall_BIO)
y_test=training_scores_encodedPD

```

In this block of code we call the *plot_confusion_matrix* function defined in the previous step, first with non-normalised values and then with values normalised from 0-1:

```

Ynames=['0', '1', '2']

np.set_printoptions(precision=2)

#          Plot          non-normalized          confusion          matrix
plot_confusion_matrix(y_test,          y_pred_test,          classes=Ynames,
                    title='Confusion matrix, without normalization')

#          Plot          normalized          confusion          matrix
plot_confusion_matrix(y_test,          y_pred_test,          classes=Ynames,          normalize=True,
                    title='Normalized confusion matrix')

plt.show()

```

Confusion matrix, without normalization

```

[[3 0 0]
 [0 3 1]
 [0 2 6]]

```

Normalized confusion matrix

```

[[1.  0.  0. ]
 [0.  0.75 0.25]
 [0.  0.25 0.75]]

```


Figure 18. Illustration of the non-normalised and normalised confusion matrices arising from the `plot_confusion_matrix` function.

Finally, we print the accuracy results, comparing the predictions (`y_pred_test`) to the actual Y values (`y_test`).

```
print("Accuracy :", metrics.accuracy_score(y_test, y_pred_test))
```

Accuracy : 0.8

This model is now ready to be shared over Jaqpot. It should be stressed that shared models should go through rigorous validation and testing by the user to guarantee high quality. Feedback on model quality is enabled in the NanoCommons platform through the Discussion tab of every model, as presented in Deliverable D5.4 “First predictive nanoQSAR models integrated into NanoCommons Knowledge Base” (the Discussions tab of a model in Jaqpot 5 is shown in Figure 38 of D5.4).

3.5. Uploading the predictive model to Jaqpot

The predictive model developed in section 3.4 can now be shared with the community with just one line of code. There are detailed instructions on how to automatically create a Jaqpot web service from a local python model at the jaqpotpy documentation, available at <https://jaqpotpy.readthedocs.io/>.

3.5.1. Setting up Jaqpot

First we need to establish a connection to Jaqpot with a valid username and password. Please note that this connection is of limited duration as a security precaution. Users may obtain a username with their email address as described in D5.4 “First predictive nanoQSAR models integrated into NanoCommons Knowledge Base”, or use the new capability that allows them to log in with their Google or Github accounts. Separate usernames should currently be used for the Knowledge Base.

```
jaqpot = Jaqpot("https://api.jaqpot.org/jaqpot/services/")
jaqpot.request_key_safe()
```

Username: filippod

Password:

3.5.2. Uploading model to Jaqpot- From model to web service

The model is then transformed into a web service using `jaqpot.deploy_pipeline`. Please note that here we use this command with a model, but in fact we could upload to Jaqpot a pipeline: this allows users to include in the model that they will share with the community, not only the mathematical model, but also the preprocessing steps that have to be performed on the dataset before reaching the point of model training, for example variable manipulations, with the limitation that actions must be performed with the scikit-learn library. For the sake of assigning more time to model sharing, the `jaqpot.deploy_pipeline` will be demonstrated for uploading only a mathematical model, without the preprocessing steps.

The general `jaqpot.deploy_pipeline` command is used like this:

`jaqpot.deploy_pipeline(pipeline,X,Y,title,description,algorithm)`

The pipeline parameters are:

- **pipeline** : sklearn pipeline model is a trained model that occurs from the sklearn.linear_model family of algorithms.
- **X** : The pandas dataframe that is used to train the model (X variables).
- **y** : The pandas dataframe that is used to train the model (y variables).
- **title**: A string containing the title of the model.
- **description**: A string containing the description of the model.
- **algorithm**: A string containing the algorithm that the model implements.

```
url=jaqpot.deploy_pipeline(clf,Xall_BIO,training_scores_encodedPD,"Jaqpot+Biomax
: D4.6 example on hackathon data","Logistic Regression","linearmodel")
url
```

2019-06-21 11:41:33,087 - INFO - Model with id: ED40iHAXQdtCDpl4NPX created. Please visit the application to proceed

As can be seen from the output, the model was successfully created with the 'ED40iHAXQdtCDpl4NPX' id and can be used immediately to get predictions, which will be shown in section 3.6, using the id of the model that has been stored in the url variable.

Please note that at the same time that the model with the id 'ED40iHAXQdtCDpl4NPX' became available as a web service, it also became available through Jaqpot's user interface at the URI: <https://app.jaqpot.org/model/ED40iHAXQdtCDpl4NPX> (Figure 19).

For a more detailed presentation of Jaqpot, please consult Deliverable D5.4 "First predictive nanoQSAR models integrated into NanoCommons Knowledge Base".

Figure 19. The model produced by the user, as accessed at the Jaqpot platform.

3.6. Generating predictions from a Jaqpot model

Using `jaqpot.predict` and providing the DataFrame for the input variable and the model id (stored in the url variable), we receive predictions that we store in the `dfJQ_Biomax` variable. We then print the values for this variable. The `predicts_Biomax` variable contains the name of the column predicted.

```
dfJQ_Biomax, predicts_Biomax = jaqpot.predict(Xall_BIO, modelId=url)
dfJQ_Biomax
```

D4.6 Description of tools for automated data mining

	..Coating	..Surface Modification	..Type of Coating	ViabCellBins	..Zeta (mV)	..Type	..Geometric Surface Area (nm ²)	..Shape	..Nominal Size (nm)	..DLS (nm)	..PDI	..Electrophoretic mobility (μcm/Vs)
0	3	0	1	2	-21.80	2	1206.874234	2	20	28.90	0.110	0.0879
1	4	0	2	2	25.90	2	1206.874234	2	20	23.48	0.172	2.0300
10	5	0	3	1	32.90	1	84.948665	2	20	269.50	0.291	2.3810
11	5	0	3	1	56.40	1	1754.460000	0	33	257.70	0.510	4.0850
12	5	0	3	0	-20.30	4	35155.320080	6	150	411.80	0.239	-1.5940
13	5	0	3	0	-5.52	0	1398.217746	2	15	27.36	0.471	-0.3994
14	5	0	3	0	-5.52	0	1398.217746	2	15	27.36	0.471	-0.3994
2	3	0	0	2	-31.70	2	1206.874234	2	20	25.24	0.174	-2.4840
3	5	0	3	1	20.50	3	180.271745	2	10	1325.00	0.277	1.6050
4	2	0	1	2	17.30	3	224.541375	5	10	3185.00	0.240	1.3610
5	1	0	1	2	5.30	3	325.380000	4	10	4391.00	0.172	0.4158
6	0	0	1	2	17.10	3	1159.260000	4	10	3109.00	0.177	1.3440
7	5	2	3	1	23.00	3	2828.925645	1	20	1609.00	0.895	1.8040
8	5	1	3	2	25.30	3	4404.764228	1	20	403.00	0.810	1.9810
9	5	0	3	1	41.00	3	3532.494233	3	70	172.40	0.183	3.2170

4. NanoCommons Knowledge Base access within KNIME through Enalos APIs

KNIME³ is a powerful open-source analytics platform used for solving cheminformatics and nanoinformatics problems. NovaMechanics through Enalos Web APIs facilitates tasks performed in molecular modeling and allows access, data mining and manipulation for multiple databases through the KNIME interface. With the aid of Enalos APIs and nodes (through a server-client architecture) (Varsou et al. 2018), the user can automate common procedures that greatly facilitate the rapid workflow prototyping within KNIME. Methods and techniques are presented in a way to offer a deeper understanding of the theoretical background of the incorporated functionalities. Here we will demonstrate the usefulness of the Enalos NanoCommons KB node in accessing and analysing different toxicity and physicochemical datasets.

Within NanoCommons, a KNIME node has been developed in order to give access to the publicly available datasets in the NanoCommons Knowledge Base through Enalos APIs. Physicochemical characterisation, toxicological and omics data (such as DLS, Zeta potential, TEM size, % of viable cells, IC50, gene expression data) can be accessed in a data matrix format for further analysis directly from within the KNIME analytics platform, as shown in Figure 20.

Enalos NanoCommons Knowledgebase

This KNIME nodes give access to NanoCommons Knowledgebase nanomaterials datasets through Enalos APIs.

Physicochemical, toxicological and omics characterisation data such as DLS, Zeta, TEM size % of viable cells, IC50, gene expression data etc can be downloaded in a data matrix format for further analysis with in the KNIME analytics platform.

Ports

Output Ports	
0	Data matrix format of Physchem or Toxicity Data

This node is contained in *Node extension for KNIME Workbench* provided by *NanoCommons Project*.

Figure 20. Enalos NanoCommons KB KNIME node.

³ <https://www.knime.com/>

4.1. Extracting datasets from NanoCommons KB within KNIME through Enalos APIs

A brief demonstration of the use of the **Enalos NanoCommons Knowledge Base** node is presented here in the form of an example workflow for data extraction and manipulation shown in Figure 21. Data extraction can be achieved in just a few steps.

Figure 21. A simple KNIME workflow for data extraction from NanoCommons KB and filtering.

Available also as a TA application:

<https://infrastructure.nanocommons.eu/services/26/nanocommons-knowledgebase-access-within-knime-through-enalos-apis/>

The **Enalos NanoCommons Knowledgebase** node configuration panel is presented in Figure 22. Users can select the dataset of interest by clicking the “Name” dropdown menu (Figure 23) and the type of data they want to extract (toxicity or physicochemical data) from the corresponding menu (Figure 24). When one of the available datasets is selected, a short description is presented on the right side of the window and the number of available measurements for each type of data (toxicity or physicochemical characterisation) is also presented.

D4.6 Description of tools for automated data mining

Figure 22: Enalos NanoCommons KB node configuration window.

Figure 23. Dataset selection.

Figure 24. Type of data selection (Toxicity or Physchem).

D4.6 Description of tools for automated data mining

In the case presented here, a toxicity dataset produced by the JRC during the FP7 NanoMILE project is selected. Executing the node generated a table which includes all the available measurements for the selected dataset (Figure 25).

Row ID	D_Misc	S_Lipid	D_Lipid	S_Aruck	D_Aruck	S_Total	D_Total	S_Fract	D_Fract	S_Cyto	D_Cyto	S_Levet	D_Levet	S_CellD	D_CellD	S
Row 0	-0.568		-0.464		0.412		-0.632		-0.181		-0.869					
Row 1	-0.326		0.436		-0.033		-1.267		0.537		-0.97					
Row 2	-1.26		-0.302		0.683		-0.732		0.476		-1.389					
Row 3	0.406		-0.846		0.676		-0.598		0.281		-0.791					
Row 4	-0.225		-0.529		-0.035		-0.844		0.423		-0.824					
Row 5	-0.775		-0.327		0.851		-0.464		-0.328		-0.79					
Row 6	-0.912		-0.641		0.798		-1.113		-0.347		-0.996					
Row 7	0.3		-0.069		-0.658		-0.02		0.887		-0.562					
Row 8	-0.374		-0.116		1.004		-0.092		-0.556		-0.711					
Row 9	-0.798		0.375		1.348		0.28		-0.663		-0.908					
Row 10	-0.033		-0.405		0.792		-0.736		-0.28		-0.966					
Row 11	-0.002		-0.244		0.321		-0.843		-0.086		-0.407					
Row 12	-1.261		-0.258		1.064		-1.286		0.379		-0.425					
Row 13	-1.201		-0.468		0.807		-0.333		-0.258		-0.812					
Row 14	-0.865		-0.411		1.117		-0.29		-0.366		-0.943					
Row 15	-0.832		-0.538		0.363		-0.437		-0.111		-1.064					
Row 16	-0.685		-0.718		0.416		-0.677		-0.305		-1.045					
Row 17	-0.662		-0.649		1.579		-0.796		-0.365		-1.321					
Row 18	-0.968		-0.793		0.263		-0.924		0.468		-1.096					
Row 19	-1.317		-0.213		0.747		-0.676		0.54		-1.877					
Row 20	-0.226		-0.516		1.004		-0.511		0.03		-1.673					
Row 21	-1.046		-0.096		0.446		-1.125		-0.305		-0.617					
Row 22	-0.375		-0.968		1.462		-0.662		0.09		-1.976					
Row 23	-0.298		0.161		0.858		0.363		-0.387		-1.265					
Row 24	-0.426		-0.332		1.603		-0.846		-0.481		-1.783					
Row 25	-0.633		-0.78		0.6		-0.591		0.465		-2.047					
Row 26	-1.235		0.303		1.639		-0.244		-1.473		0.994					
Row 27	-0.008		0.127		0.011		-0.478		-0.046		0.302					
Row 28	-0.282		0.626		1.192		-0.274		-1.32		0.39					
Row 29	-1.041		0.231		0.828		-0.568		-0.088		-0.628					
Row 30	-0.393		-0.48		0.682		-0.08		-0.75		0.5					
Row 31	0.275		0.558		0.896		0.405		-0.722		0.289					
Row 32	-1.167		-0.148		0.211		-0.769		-0.274		-0.403					
Row 33	0.074		0.526		1.303		0.554		-0.938		-0.633					
Row 34	0.793		0.714		0.242		0.631		-0.801		0.877					
Row 35	-0.787		0.602		1.927		0.943		-1.552		0.142					
Row 36	0.642		0.43		1.349		0.294		-1.186		-0.006					

Figure 25. Extracted data from JRC toxicity dataset (NanoMILE project).

This dataset includes 188 columns of data. However it is possible that each dataset has missing values. For this reason, we can filter out the columns that do not contain any data using the standard KNIME **Missing Value Column Filter** node (Figures 21 and 26). The filtered table is presented in Figure 27.

D4.6 Description of tools for automated data mining

Figure 26. Missing Value Column Filter node configuration panel.

Row ID	S Measurement	D _Viable	D _Nucle	D _Nucle	D _Cell	D _Mitoc	D _Lipid	D _Nucle	D _Total	D _Pract	D _Cyto	S Particle	S Tax Info-Measur...	S Tax Inf...
Row 0	TDK000000000197	1.09	0.486	-0.473	-0.503	-0.568	-0.464	0.412	-0.852	-0.181	-0.869	NP00192	Dose_0_1_RIC_AL000564	HepaRG
Row 1	TDK000000000198	-0.398	0.02	-0.581	0.075	-0.326	0.436	-0.033	-1.307	0.557	-0.97	NP00255	Dose_0_1_RIC_AL000122	HepaRG
Row 2	TDK000000000199	-1.133	-0.369	-0.956	-0.774	-1.26	-0.302	0.683	-0.732	0.476	-1.389	NP00259	Dose_0_1_RIC_AL000567	HepaRG
Row 3	TDK000000000200	-0.652	0.526	-0.582	0.246	0.406	-0.846	0.676	-0.988	0.281	-0.791	NP00175	Dose_0_1_RIC_AL000424	HepaRG
Row 4	TDK000000000201	-0.384	0.27	-0.05	-0.308	-0.225	-0.529	-0.038	-0.844	0.423	-0.824	NP00144	Dose_0_1_RIC_AL000566	HepaRG
Row 5	TDK000000000202	-0.64	0.339	0.265	-0.139	-0.775	-0.527	0.871	-0.464	-0.328	-0.78	NP00258	Dose_0_1_RIC_AL000153	HepaRG
Row 6	TDK000000000203	-0.769	0.331	-0.176	-0.763	-0.912	-0.645	0.738	-1.113	-0.347	-0.996	NP00283	Dose_0_1_RIC_AL000570	HepaRG
Row 7	TDK000000000204	-0.469	-0.223	0.123	0.275	0.3	-0.069	-0.658	-0.02	0.307	-0.582	NP00114	Dose_0_1_RIC_AL000565	HepaRG
Row 8	TDK000000000205	-0.825	0.204	-0.032	0.01	-0.374	-0.116	1.004	-0.692	-0.556	-0.711	NP00257	Dose_0_1_RIC_AL000143	HepaRG
Row 9	TDK000000000206	-0.366	0.428	0.139	-0.887	-0.758	0.375	1.348	-0.463	-0.908	-0.908	NP00283	Dose_0_1_RIC_AL000569	HepaRG
Row 10	TDK000000000207	0.075	0.26	0.308	-0.863	-0.031	-0.405	0.751	-0.776	-0.28	-0.996	NP00193	Dose_0_1_RIC_AL000036	HepaRG
Row 11	TDK000000000208	-0.288	-0.052	-0.185	-0.223	-0.002	-0.244	0.321	-0.643	-0.086	-0.407	NP00256	Dose_0_1_RIC_AL000133	HepaRG
Row 12	TDK000000000209	-0.382	-0.128	1.067	0.065	0.381	-0.258	1.064	-1.266	0.379	-0.425	NP00282	Dose_0_1_RIC_AL000963	HepaRG
Row 13	TDK000000000210	-0.928	0.33	-0.682	-1.158	-1.201	-0.468	0.807	-0.133	-0.288	-0.812	NP00260	Dose_0_1_RIC_AL000752	HepaRG
Row 14	TDK000000000211	0.181	-0.208	-0.304	-1.388	-0.865	-0.613	1.117	-0.29	-0.763	-0.943	NP00489	Dose_0_1_RIC_AL000743	HepaRG
Row 15	TDK000000000212	-0.36	0.644	0.177	-0.487	-0.832	-0.538	0.565	-0.637	-0.115	-1.084	NP00493	Dose_0_1_RIC_AL000747	HepaRG
Row 16	TDK000000000213	-1.174	0.586	-0.893	-1.585	-0.985	-0.736	0.438	-0.877	-0.205	-1.059	NP00497	Dose_0_1_RIC_AL000751	HepaRG
Row 17	TDK000000000214	-1.342	-0.083	-0.383	-0.494	-0.662	-0.449	1.579	-0.796	-0.765	-1.313	NP00488	Dose_0_1_RIC_AL000742	HepaRG
Row 18	TDK000000000215	-1.085	1.139	0.148	-0.338	-0.968	-0.753	0.383	-0.924	0.468	-1.096	NP00492	Dose_0_1_RIC_AL000746	HepaRG
Row 19	TDK000000000216	-0.818	0.325	-0.747	-1.154	-1.117	-0.213	0.747	-0.675	0.54	-1.877	NP00496	Dose_0_1_RIC_AL000750	HepaRG
Row 20	TDK000000000217	-0.176	0.159	0.002	-1.094	-0.226	-0.516	1.004	-0.511	0.03	-1.639	NP00487	Dose_0_1_RIC_AL000745	HepaRG
Row 21	TDK000000000218	-1.768	0.406	-1.038	-0.013	-1.046	-0.056	0.446	-1.125	-0.205	-0.617	NP00491	Dose_0_1_RIC_AL000745	HepaRG
Row 22	TDK000000000219	-1.833	1.137	-0.094	0.091	-0.875	-0.608	1.402	-0.662	0.09	-1.676	NP00495	Dose_0_1_RIC_AL000749	HepaRG
Row 23	TDK000000000220	-0.268	-0.596	-0.56	-0.428	-0.298	0.381	0.858	0.163	-0.387	-1.295	NP00486	Dose_0_1_RIC_AL000748	HepaRG
Row 24	TDK000000000221	-1.185	0.018	-0.565	0.675	-0.826	0.332	1.603	-0.845	-0.481	-1.783	NP00490	Dose_0_1_RIC_AL000744	HepaRG
Row 25	TDK000000000222	-0.561	0.308	-0.021	-0.026	-0.651	-0.75	0.6	-0.991	0.455	-2.047	NP00494	Dose_0_1_RIC_AL000748	HepaRG
Row 26	TDK000000000223	-0.663	0.377	0.028	-0.389	-1.235	0.203	1.639	-0.244	-1.475	0.994	NP00382	Dose_1_RIC_AL000563	HepaRG
Row 27	TDK000000000224	-0.82	0.249	-0.693	-1.191	-0.008	0.127	0.011	-0.478	-0.046	0.102	NP00192	Dose_1_RIC_AL000564	HepaRG
Row 28	TDK000000000225	-0.448	0.404	-0.159	-0.221	-0.282	0.838	1.182	-0.274	-1.32	0.39	NP00255	Dose_1_RIC_AL000122	HepaRG
Row 29	TDK000000000226	-1.218	-0.132	-1.409	-1.044	-1.041	0.221	0.838	-0.568	-0.088	-0.428	NP00259	Dose_1_RIC_AL000567	HepaRG
Row 30	TDK000000000227	0.517	0.477	-0.668	-0.364	-0.293	-0.48	0.682	-0.08	-0.75	0.5	NP00275	Dose_1_RIC_AL000564	HepaRG
Row 31	TDK000000000228	-0.165	0.175	-0.158	0.768	0.275	0.938	0.896	0.405	-0.722	0.269	NP00114	Dose_1_RIC_AL000564	HepaRG
Row 32	TDK000000000229	-1.449	0.92	-0.383	-0.963	-1.107	-0.148	0.211	-0.768	-0.274	-0.403	NP00258	Dose_1_RIC_AL000153	HepaRG
Row 33	TDK000000000230	0.406	0.297	0.499	-0.179	0.074	0.526	1.303	0.554	-0.938	-0.633	NP00283	Dose_1_RIC_AL000170	HepaRG
Row 34	TDK000000000231	-0.31	0.2	0.571	1.307	0.795	0.714	0.242	0.631	-0.801	0.877	NP00114	Dose_1_RIC_AL000565	HepaRG
Row 35	TDK000000000232	-1.471	0.725	-0.581	0.03	-0.787	0.602	1.927	0.943	-1.552	0.142	NP00257	Dose_1_RIC_AL000143	HepaRG
Row 36	TDK000000000233	0.145	0.11	0.131	-0.136	0.642	0.40	1.349	0.194	-1.088	-0.006	NP00283	Dose_1_RIC_AL000569	HepaRG

Figure 27. Produced table containing only the columns that do not contain missing entries.

The same steps can be repeated for the JRC physicochemical data. In the final part of the workflow we combine the two produced tables. To achieve that, we used the standard **Joiner** node combining the tables using the column containing the nanoparticles ID available in both tables (Figure 28).

Figure 28. Joiner node configuration panel.

The produced table contains all the physicochemical data for each toxicological entry. Using a **Column Filter** node we can keep only the properties of interest (Figure 29).

D4.6 Description of tools for automated data mining

Figure 29. Final data table, containing both toxicity and physicochemical data in a data matrix format ready for further computational analysis.

4.2. Enalos APIs for NanoCommons Knowledgebase

NovaM implemented a client-server architecture in order to be able to provide access to the publicly available NanoCommons KB datasets through the KNIME analytics platform interface.

A server has been set up using the SOAP Web API in order to retrieve toxicity and/or physicochemical datasets needed information from the KB and feed them to the Client (Enalos NanoCommons KB KNIME node). Enalos NanoCommons KB KNIME node (acts as Client) has an interactive configuration interface and can be updated automatically following any changes in the database using the first web service (see below). The KNIME node as an output provides the requested toxicity or physicochemical properties in a data matrix format.

Full description of the SOAP API of the Enalos web service in Web Service definition language is available at <http://enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebServices/KnimeDBWebService?wsdl> and reproduced in its current form below:

```
<wsdl:definitions xmlns:xsd="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
xmlns:wsdl="http://schemas.xmlsoap.org/wsdl/"
xmlns:tns="http://knimedatabase.enaloswebservices/"
xmlns:soap="http://schemas.xmlsoap.org/wsdl/soap/"
xmlns:ns1="http://schemas.xmlsoap.org/soap/http" name="KnimeDBWebServiceService"
targetNamespace="http://knimedatabase.enaloswebservices/">
<wsdl:types>
<xs:schema xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
xmlns:tns="http://knimedatabase.enaloswebservices/"
xmlns:ns1="http://jaxb.dev.java.net/array" attributeFormDefault="unqualified"
elementFormDefault="unqualified"
```

D4.6 Description of tools for automated data mining

```

targetNamespace="http://knimedatabase.enaloswebservices/">
<xs:import namespace="http://jaxb.dev.java.net/array"/>
<xs:element name="getDatasetData" type="tns:getDatasetData"/>
<xs:element name="getDatasetDataResponse" type="tns:getDatasetDataResponse"/>
<xs:element name="getExistingDatasets" type="tns:getExistingDatasets"/>
<xs:element name="getExistingDatasetsResponse" type="tns:getExistingDatasetsResponse"/>
<xs:complexType name="getDatasetData">
<xs:sequence>
<xs:element name="datasetID" type="xs:int"/>
<xs:element minOccurs="0" name="typeOfData" type="xs:string"/>
</xs:sequence>
</xs:complexType>
<xs:complexType name="getDatasetDataResponse">
<xs:sequence>
<xs:element minOccurs="0" name="return" type="tns:datasetDBDResponse"/>
</xs:sequence>
</xs:complexType>
<xs:complexType name="datasetDBDResponse">
<xs:sequence>
<xs:element maxOccurs="unbounded" minOccurs="0" name="data" nillable="true"
type="ns1:stringArray"/>
<xs:element maxOccurs="unbounded" minOccurs="0" name="datatypes" nillable="true"
type="xs:string"/>
<xs:element maxOccurs="unbounded" minOccurs="0" name="headers" nillable="true"
type="xs:string"/>
</xs:sequence>
</xs:complexType>
<xs:complexType name="getExistingDatasets">
<xs:sequence/>
</xs:complexType>
<xs:complexType name="getExistingDatasetsResponse">
<xs:sequence>
<xs:element minOccurs="0" name="return" type="tns:datasetDBDResponse"/>
</xs:sequence>
</xs:complexType>
</xs:schema>
<xs:schema xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
targetNamespace="http://jaxb.dev.java.net/array" version="1.0">
<xs:complexType final="#all" name="stringArray">
<xs:sequence>
<xs:element maxOccurs="unbounded" minOccurs="0" name="item" nillable="true"
type="xs:string"/>
</xs:sequence>
</xs:complexType>
</xs:schema>
</wsdl:types>
<wsdl:message name="getDatasetDataResponse">
<wsdl:part element="tns:getDatasetDataResponse" name="parameters"> </wsdl:part>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="getExistingDatasets">
<wsdl:part element="tns:getExistingDatasets" name="parameters"> </wsdl:part>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="getExistingDatasetsResponse">
<wsdl:part element="tns:getExistingDatasetsResponse" name="parameters"> </wsdl:part>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="getDatasetData">
<wsdl:part element="tns:getDatasetData" name="parameters"> </wsdl:part>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:portType name="KnimeDBWebService">
<wsdl:operation name="getDatasetData">
<wsdl:input message="tns:getDatasetData" name="getDatasetData"> </wsdl:input>
<wsdl:output message="tns:getDatasetDataResponse" name="getDatasetDataResponse">

```

```

</wsdl:output>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="getExistingDatasets">
<wsdl:input message="tns:getExistingDatasets" name="getExistingDatasets"> </wsdl:input>
<wsdl:output message="tns:getExistingDatasetsResponse"
name="getExistingDatasetsResponse"> </wsdl:output>
</wsdl:operation>
</wsdl:portType>
<wsdl:binding name="KnimeDBWebServiceServiceSoapBinding" type="tns:KnimeDBWebService">
<soap:binding style="document" transport="http://schemas.xmlsoap.org/soap/http"/>
<wsdl:operation name="getDatasetData">
<soap:operation soapAction="" style="document"/>
<wsdl:input name="getDatasetData">
<soap:body use="literal"/>
</wsdl:input>
<wsdl:output name="getDatasetDataResponse">
<soap:body use="literal"/>
</wsdl:output>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="getExistingDatasets">
<soap:operation soapAction="" style="document"/>
<wsdl:input name="getExistingDatasets">
<soap:body use="literal"/>
</wsdl:input>
<wsdl:output name="getExistingDatasetsResponse">
<soap:body use="literal"/>
</wsdl:output>
</wsdl:operation>
</wsdl:binding>
<wsdl:service name="KnimeDBWebServiceService">
<wsdl:port binding="tns:KnimeDBWebServiceServiceSoapBinding"
name="KnimeDBWebServicePort">
<soap:address location="http://localhost:80/EnalosWebServices/KnimeDBWebService"/>
</wsdl:port>
</wsdl:service>
</wsdl:definitions>

```

There are two calls through Enalos web services for retrieving data from the NanoCommons KB:

- a) getExistingDatasets
- b) getDatasetDate

The first web service is an xml request with the following format:

```

<soapenv:Envelope xmlns:soapenv="http://schemas.xmlsoap.org/soap/envelope/"
xmlns:knim="http://knimedatabase.enaloswebservices/">
  <soapenv:Header/>
  <soapenv:Body>
    <knim:getExistingDatasets/>
  </soapenv:Body>
</soapenv:Envelope>

```

There is no need for specific arguments and the node automatically receives all the available datasets with the relevant information:

1. The internal number id of the dataset

D4.6 Description of tools for automated data mining

2. The title of the dataset
3. A short description of the dataset
4. The number of the entries of the physicochemical entries of the dataset
5. The number of the entries of the toxicity entries of the dataset

The particular web service is used in order to define the configuration interface of the provided KNIME node.

The second web service is an xml request with the following format:

```
<soapenv:Envelope xmlns:soapenv="http://schemas.xmlsoap.org/soap/envelope/"
xmlns:knim="http://knimedatabase.enaloswebservices/">
  <soapenv:Header/>
  <soapenv:Body>
    <knim:getDatasetData>
      <datasetID>1</datasetID>
      <typeOfData>PhysChems</typeOfData>
    </knim:getDatasetData>
  </soapenv:Body>
</soapenv:Envelope>
```

This web service requires two arguments:

1. The unique ID of the requested dataset for retrieval
2. The type of data for retrieval that can be either "Toxs" for the toxicity data or "PhysChems" for the physicochemical data

The webservice is replying with a number of "headers" and the same number of "datatypes", as well as a number of "data" that are structures that contain "items" of the same number as "headers" and "datatypes" with a one-to-one relationship between them.

These received data are shown in the "output" of the KNIME node.

5. Data retrieval from eNanoMapper instances

The eNanoMapper database is developed and maintained by IdeaConsult and due to its popularity as data management platform for different EU nanosafety projects, the integration into the NanoCommons KB is of highest importance to allow harmonised access to these data sources. Here we describe the data access options offered by the systems, which are the starting point for this integration. Data stored in the eNanoMapper database and other data warehouses based on this platform is accessible via the AMBIT REST API⁴. The user can for example use the R programming language to use the API to retrieve data from the eNanoMapper database. A Jupyter notebook was created to showcase the retrieval of data using the API⁵. In this notebook, all available file formats were retrieved for the NanoWiki dataset. Retrieval of the NanoWiki dataset in RDF format (Jeliazkova et al. 2015) only takes a couple of lines of code.

Firstly, the user needs to install two required R-packages: `httr` and `jsonlite`. After installation of these packages the user can set variables which are used in the GET function from the `httr` package.

```
datasetID <- "20"  
startPage <- 0  
pageSize <- "all"  
path <- "https://data.enanomapper.net:443"
```

The `datasetID` is the identifier of the NanoWiki dataset, in this case 20. The `startPage` is 0 and the `pageSize` is "all" as we would like to include all data from the dataset in this example. The user can change these variables. The `path` variable is the path that connects the user to the eNanoMapper database. In this example the path is <https://data.enanomapper.net:443>.

```
request_bundle <- GET(url = path, path = paste0("bundle/", datasetID,  
"/substance"), query = list(  
mergeDatasets = F,  
page = startPage,  
pagesize = pageSize,  
media = "text/n3"),  
write_disk(paste0("bundle_", datasetID, "_RDF.n3"), overwrite = T))
```

The data in RDF format is retrieved using the GET function. Additionally, this API call is stored in a variable named `request_bundle` in R itself. The `datasetID` is pasted in the path string, where the extension to the path variable is placed. The path variable is called by the "url =" part of the GET function. Merging the datasets is set to `FALSE` as we only retrieve one dataset in this example. The page and pagesize were set by the user beforehand. The media is set to retrieve the RDF file format. Finally, the file is saved in the working directory the user is in under the name "bundle_20_RDF.n3", and overwritten if it already exists. The full Jupyter notebook provides additional examples for all available

⁴ <http://enanomapper.github.io/API/>

⁵ https://github.com/OpenRiskNet/notebooks/blob/master/eNanoMapper/eNanoMapper_API.ipynb

file formats for the NanoWiki database.

6. Similarity search tools

The concept of similarity is central to predictive toxicology as both QSAR modelling and read-across approaches are based on similarities among substances. Especially in nanoinformatics, similarity definition is not trivial, due to the multi-perspective characterisation of NMs (physicochemical, biological, kinetics etc.), which produces long and complex fingerprints that may contain both numerical data and categorical variables. Therefore, it is of great importance to complement the exact search tools that have been presented so far in this deliverable with tools that are based on similarity search methods and can take into account the complexity involved in NMs characterisation. This section presents the similarity search tool developed in NanoCommons that allows a user to first select the variables of interest, and then assign specific values to them and search through the KB for similar NMs, i.e. for NMs for which a distance metric is below a threshold value. The service gives many options for selecting the distance metric for both numerical and categorical data.

Categorical data refer to values or observations of descriptive nature, which, as opposed to numerical data, are not inherently ordered, but can rather be sorted into qualitative groups or categories. Categorical data are of great importance in data mining and knowledge discovery, but they lack inherent mathematical meaning. We follow here an approach to perform distance-based learning tasks with categorical data which involves assigning an arbitrary numerical value to each category and then calculating distances based on numerical metrics like the Euclidean or the Manhattan distance.

The similarity search tool, developed by NTUA, is constructed as follows. Firstly, all data or parts of the data are retrieved using the tools presented in the previous section. Then, the user chooses all or a subset of the NMs characteristics included in the dataset and assigns to them specific values to which the NM should be similar to. Based on this selection, the tool then searches through the dataset for NMs which are similar with respect to the selected characteristics.

For the similarity tool three Python functions were developed integrating pairwise distances functions that are available through the metrics package the scikit learn library. Before using the tools, all data has been loaded into a Pandas DataFrame. The three functions are provided in Appendix 1 and are briefly explained here:

- The *all_numerical* function converts categorical data contained in the dataframe to numerical data by substituting strings with consecutive unique integer values. This allows for calculating similarity distances, even in the presence of categorical data.
- The function *prepare_query()* is a function that assists the user in preparing the query. The input to this function is the available pandas DataFrame. The *all_numerical* function is called first, to convert strings to numerical values. The response of the function is a Python dictionary that contains all the information needed for defining the query, namely the parameter names and the numerical values corresponding to the strings of categorical variables. It also contains a null query with all the available keys. Based on this information, the user constructs his/her query by selecting the desired keys and filling the values that define the NM of interest.
- The *similarity_search* function implements the query search. The inputs are:
 1. The available pandas dataframe that will be searched upon.

2. The query defined by the user.
3. The metric that will be used for similarity search, one among the following options: 'cityblock', 'cosine', 'euclidean', 'l1', 'l2', 'manhattan', 'braycurtis', 'canberra', 'chebyshev', 'correlation', 'dice', 'hamming', 'jaccard', 'kulsinski', 'mahalanobis', 'minkowski', 'rogerstanimoto', 'russellrao', 'seuclidean', 'sokalmichener', 'sokalsneath', 'sqeuclidean', 'yule'. For exact definitions of these metrics please refer to Appendix 2 in this deliverable.
4. The number of similar NMs that will be returned.

The response contains two arrays. The first one returns the IDs of similar NMs. The second array contains the actual distance calculated using the chosen metric. The order of appearance is from the most similar to less similar NMs to the query NM.

The similarity search tool is demonstrated on the DataFrame produced in section 3.2.1, after retrieving data contained in the NanoCommons KB. The goal in this example is to search for NMs in the DataFrame which are similar to a NM whose nominal size is 80 nm and DLS is 19.6 nm.

6.1. Import the required packages

First the required packages should be imported.

```
import getpass
import requests
import sys
import http.client as http_client
import logging
import json
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
from sklearn.metrics import pairwise_distances_argmin, pairwise_distances
pd.set_option('mode.chained_assignment', None)
```

6.2. Json / Python Dictionary query

The *prepare_query* function is applied on the dataframe and produces the following output. Firstly, the NMs contained in the dataframe are presented. Then all categorical values are presented (in our example Type, Coating, Type of Coating, Shape) with the conversions from strings to integers. Finally the null query is displayed, containing all the keys (variables) that can be selected for defining the query of interest.

```
{
  'Id': {
    'Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00192': 0,
    'Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00193': 1,
    'Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00214a': 2,
    'Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00214b': 3,
```

```

      'Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00254': 4,
      'Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00255': 5,
      'Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00256': 6,
      'Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00257': 7,
      'Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00258': 8,
      'Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00259': 9,
      'Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00260': 10,
      'Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00262': 11,
      'Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00266': 12,
      'Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00269': 13,
      'Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00282': 14,
      'Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00283': 15
    }
  } {
    '..Type': {
      'Ag': 0,
      'Ce': 1,
      'Si': 2,
      'Ti': 3,
      'Zn': 4
    }
  } {
    '..Coating': {
      'AA4040': 0,
      'F127': 1,
      'PVP': 2,
      'aminoacid': 3,
      'aminoalkyl': 4,
      'triethoxycaprilylsilane': 5,
      'uncoated': 6
    }
  } {
    '..Type of Coating': {
      'negative': 0,
      'neutral': 1,
      'positive': 2,
      'uncoated': 3
    }
  } {
    '..Shape': {
      'Cubic': 0,
      'Nanorods': 1,
      'Spherical': 2,
      'Spherical/ Square': 3,
      'Square': 4,
      'Square/Spherical/Rods': 5,
      'Various Shapes': 6,
      'Various shapes': 7
    }
  }

```

D4.6 Description of tools for automated data mining

```

}
Import the query values needed on the following object: {
  '_.Nominal Size (nm)': None,
  '_.DLS (nm)': None,
  '_.DLS SD (nm)': None,
  '_.PDI': None,
  '_.PDI SD': None,
  '_.Zeta (mV)': None,
  '_.Zeta SD (mV)': None,
  '_.Electrophoretic mobility (µcm/Vs)': None,
  '_.Electrophoretic mobility SD (µcm/Vs)': None,
  '_.TEM (nm)': None,
  '_.TEM SD (nm)': None,
  '_.TEM Shortest (nm)': None,
  '_.TEM Shortest SD (nm)': None,
  '_.TEM Longest (nm)': None,
  '_.TEM Longest SD (nm)': None,
  '_.STEM (nm)': None,
  '_.STEM SD (nm)': None,
  '_.BET (m2/g)': None,
  '_.BET SD(m2/g)': None,
  '_.Energy Band Gap (eV)': None,
  '_.Geometric Surface Area (nm2)': None,
  'Id': None,
  '..Type': None,
  '..Coating': None,
  '..Type of Coating': None,
  '..Shape': None
}
}

```

In our example, we define a query by selecting Nominal Size and DLS as variables of interest and search for NMs in the DataFrame similar to both nominal size = 80 nm and DLS = 19.6 nm. The search is performed using the cosine similarity metric and we search for the 10 most similar materials to the query NM.

```

query = {'_.Nominal Size (nm)':80, '_.DLS (nm)':19.6}
similarity_search(df, query, "cosine", 10)

```

The results produced are shown next: Firstly, the similar NMs are presented with both the original identifiers and the IDs from the original dataframe sorted from the most similar to the least similar to the query NM. The exact distance metrics are shown next.

```

([Name: Id, dtype: object, 1      Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00266
  Name: Id, dtype: object, 2      Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00269

```

D4.6 Description of tools for automated data mining

```
Name: Id, dtype: object, 0      Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00262
Name: Id, dtype: object, 13     Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00283
Name: Id, dtype: object, 14     Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00214a
Name: Id, dtype: object, 9      Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00254
Name: Id, dtype: object, 12     Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00282
Name: Id, dtype: object, 11     Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00192
Name: Id, dtype: object, 10     Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00193
Name: Id, dtype: object, 8      Experiment:Hackathon:HA_NP00260
],
[0.18903538307959833,
0.2102799182610049,
0.25160957022006336,
0.3244115497203106,
0.3244115497203106,
0.4141218594159496,
0.4439846079730012,
0.6405952044167159,
0.6908082804060377,
0.7141873160664631])
```

The complete python notebook that implements this example is available at <https://github.com/NanoCommons/notebooks/blob/master/D4.6Deliverables/SimilaritySearch.ipynb>.

7. Searching services in the Jaqpot modelling platform

As demonstrated in section 3, the architecture of the Jaqpot 5 infrastructure allows users to easily deploy their own models and therefore it can serve as a central repository of models for the nanoinformatics community. It is a complete web-based modelling platform for generating, hosting, sharing and using datasets and predictive models. Details on the functionality of Jaqpot regarding Quantitative Structure Analysis Relationship (QSAR) and Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic (PBPK) modelling have been given in Deliverables D5.4 and D6.1, respectively. Jaqpot already hosts a large number of models and it is expected that this number will grow through TA projects and models deployed by third-party users. To help users in finding model(s) of interest, it is equipped with search services. In this section of the deliverable, we describe the development and use of these services.

7.1. Architecture of the Jaqpot search service

A number of state-of-the-art technologies have been utilized for the development of the indexing and searching engines for Jaqpot models.

Regarding the architecture for developing the service, we had to select among many open source solutions, such as Apache Solr and Elastic Search. We decided to use [Elastic Search](https://www.elastic.co/elasticsearch/)⁶ since it offers, from a System admin perspective, all the necessary tools that support scalability. Elastic search can index billions of documents and can be deployed through docker containers. It provides a full-text search engine with an HTTP web interface and schema-free JSON documents. Elastic Search is developed in Java following an open-source business model with many of the parts licensed under various open source licences, mostly Apache license. It is based on Lucene (another Apache project) and many official clients are available in different established programming languages.

For the management and synchronization of the search services, we used [Docker](https://www.docker.com/)⁷, which is the state-of-the-art solution for containerising microservices, and [Kubernetes](https://kubernetes.io/)⁸, which is an open-source container-orchestration system for automating application deployment, scaling, and management.

In its full operation, Jaqpot has to serve many requests, so it will need to run asynchronous methods and this requires a way for synchronization. We are utilizing [Redis In-Memory Data Storage](https://redis.io/)⁹ which runs on RAM and achieves very high speeds, since the I/O operation in RAM is very quick and does not involve storage on hard disks. The REST architecture and containerized systems are not suitable for this task, because they are not allowed to store the session on a running application.

Another aspect of such systems is messaging. Message queues provide an asynchronous communications protocol, meaning that the sender and receiver of the message do not need to interact with the message queue at the same time. Messages placed onto the queue are stored until the recipient retrieves them. Message queues have implicit or explicit limits on the size of data that may be transmitted in a single message and the number of messages that may remain outstanding on

⁶ <https://www.elastic.co/elasticsearch/>

⁷ <https://www.docker.com/>

⁸ <https://kubernetes.io/>

⁹ <https://redis.io/>

the queue. We use [Apache Kafka](https://kafka.apache.org/)¹⁰, which is an open-source stream-processing software platform developed by LinkedIn and donated to the Apache Software Foundation, written in Scala and Java. Kafka is suitable for the Jaqpot project, which aims to provide a unified, high-throughput, low-latency platform for handling real-time data feeds. Kafka can connect to external systems (for data import/export) via Kafka Connect and provides Kafka Streams, a Java stream processing library. By default, it can be connected with Elastic Search and offers a document indexing solution for searching.

The two pipelines (indexing and searching) are provided under a gateway API and are explained in the next subsections. The required microservices have been developed mainly in Java and use asynchronous messaging and an in-memory database for storing the results.

7.2. Description of Indexing

The solution developed for indexing the models is shown as a flowchart (Figure 30). When a model is deployed in Jaqpot and is stored in the database, some information is already available (model title, model creator and the independent and predicted feature names of the model). This information is used for initially indexing the model in Elastic Search. A message is produced on the message queue (Kafka) and when the consumer reads the message it proceeds with the indexing of the model. If information about the model is updated (metadata / documentation / feature info etc.) another message is produced. The message is stacked on a different message queue for the indexer to consume, this time for updating the already indexed model with the new available information. This allows messages to be stored on the message broker and consumed by the indexer. This process can be scaled, according to requirements to support millions of requests and concurrent users.

¹⁰ <https://kafka.apache.org/>

Figure 30. Jaqpot “scheme” for the indexing of entities

7.3. Description of the search service

The service for searching the indexed database is part of the Jaqpot REST API. The URL routes created work with HTTP GET method:

<https://api.jaqpot.org/jaqpot/services/search> and
<https://api.jaqpot.org/jaqpot/services/search/session> .

Jaqpot API uses Swagger for documentation (<https://api.jaqpot.org/jaqpot/swagger/>). Swagger offers a user interface that is created upon the swagger definition of an API and allows a human user to interact with the API services. Two APIs have been created offering the search Jaqpot services as shown in Figure 31.

Figure 31. Search service on Swagger UI.

D4.6 Description of tools for automated data mining

The GET/service/search method (Figure 32) needs only the “term” parameter, which is the specific keyword entered into the Jaqpot search engine for retrieving the most relevant results.

The screenshot shows a web interface for the GET /services/search endpoint. The title is "Searches for Jaqpot Entities". Below the title, there is a "Parameters" section with a "Cancel" button. The parameters table is as follows:

Name	Description
term string (query)	term

Below the table, there is an input field containing "term - term". At the bottom of the parameters section is a blue "Execute" button. Below the parameters section is a "Responses" section.

Figure 32. GET/service/search method. Starts a search session

The services respond by generating a “session” ID, which refers to the search session that has been initiated. A message is then written on the message queue with the term and the session.

This session ID is copied in the GET/service/session method (Figure 33), which needs two additional pagination parameters, namely “from”, “to” that control the number and the order of the search results that are returned by the service.

The screenshot shows a web interface for the GET /services/search/session endpoint. The title is "List of found entities through session". Below the title, there is a "Parameters" section with a "Cancel" button. The parameters table is as follows:

Name	Description
SESSION string (query)	session
from integer (query)	from
to integer (query)	to

Below the table, there are three input fields: "session - session", "from - from", and "to - to". At the bottom of the parameters section is a blue "Execute" button.

Figure 33. Search session. Receives the recourse IDs found by the search service.

D4.6 Description of tools for automated data mining

The message consumer receives both the session ID and the search term and creates a query on the indexed database, which in our case is an Elastic Search as described above. The results are stored in the REDIS database as an array under the session ID. Every new entity found in the session is appended in that array. The search session is valid for 5 minutes and then it is deleted automatically to avoid data overflow.

To provide scalability, i.e. simultaneous use by multiple users, the Jaqpot search service uses a message broker. The API can accept many calls, as search sessions are created in milliseconds. Each session produces a message, which is transferred to the consumer, while the results are stored in an in-memory storage database system. As described before, we chose REDIS since it is one of the more robust and mature systems available that offers redundancy, ships with docker and can be deployed practically in any system.

Below we provide a flow chart of the Jaqpot search services (Figure 34). The non blocking API and the in-memory data structure store follows the REST architecture, which supports scalability of systems and services.

Figure 34. Jaqpot searching service

7.4. Examples of using the Jaqpot search service

Here we present some examples of using the Jaqpot search service from both the swagger API documentation and the Jaqpot GUI.

The first example is a search over the API with the term “QMRf”. We first use the GET/service/search method as shown in Figure 35, which returns the Session ID.

The screenshot displays the Swagger API interface for the endpoint `GET /services/search`. The parameters section shows a `term` of type `string (query)` with the value `QMRf` entered in the input field. Below the parameters, there are `Execute` and `Clear` buttons. The `Responses` section shows the `Curl` command, the `Request URL` (`https://api.jaqpot.org:443/jaqpot/services/search?term=QMRf`), and the `Server response` with a `Code` of `200` and a `Response body` of `{ "searchSession": "qK1vzq6qtSp1" }`. A `Download` button is visible next to the response body.

Figure 35. Using swagger API to create a session ID for searching with the keyword “QMRf”

The session ID is entered into the GET/service/session method along with the pagination parameters “from” and “to” which are set to 0 and 5 respectively (Figure 36).

D4.6 Description of tools for automated data mining

GET /services/search/session List of found entities through session

List of found entities through session

Parameters Cancel

Name	Description
session string (query)	session <input type="text" value="qK1vrq6qXSpl"/>
from integer (query)	from <input type="text" value="0"/>
to integer (query)	to <input type="text" value="5"/>

Execute Clear

Responses

Figure 36. Using swagger API to search for entities with term “QMRF”

The service responds by returning all found entities associated with the keyword “QMRF” (Figure 37).

Server response

Code: 200

Details

Response body

```

{
  "total": 2,
  "entityId": [
    {
      "model/afwcd:FRN3ovvBhjV848",
      "model/3whRzLV3yV7LzBj7s7"
    }
  ],
  "finished": "true",
  "duration": "21"
}

```

Response headers

```

access-control-allow-headers: Content-Type, api_key, Authorisation, subjectid, Accept, total
access-control-allow-methods: GET, POST, DELETE, PUT, PATCH, OPTIONS
access-control-allow-origin: *
access-control-expose-headers: total
content-encoding: gzip
content-type: application/json
date: Mon, 23 Dec 2019 12:36:50 GMT
server: nginx/1.13.12
status: 200
strict-transport-security: max-age=15724800; includeSubDomains
vary: Accept-Encoding
x-powered-by: Undertow/1

```

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	A list of jaqpot entities found	No links

application/json

Figure 37. The response of the search service containing with a list of models containing the keyword “QMRF”

In the second example we will search for models containing the keyword “C60” using the Japrot GUI as shown in Figure 38.

D4.6 Description of tools for automated data mining

Figure 38. Search bar on Jaqpot GUI

The search service responds in only 39ms and returns the five models containing the keyword “C60” as shown in Figure 39.

The screenshot shows the Jaqpot web interface. At the top, there is a search bar with the text "Search Jaqpot". Below the search bar, the results are displayed as follows:

- Searched for:** C60
- Found:** 5 entities
- In:** 39 ms

The search results are listed in a table-like format with five entries, each containing a title, model type, description, and creation date:

Title	Model Type	Description	Created
Linear Model for Predicting Solubility of C60 Fullerenes in Various Solvents11	Neural Model		Jun 20, 2019
Neural Network Model for Predicting Solubility of C60 Fullerenes in Various Solvents	Neural Model	Shared with: Lab of Process Control and Informatics NanoCommons	Apr 19, 2019
Linear Model for Predicting Solubility of C60 Fullerenes in Various Solvents11	Neural Model		Jun 19, 2019
Linear QSPR modeling of fullerene C60 solubility in organic solvents with Multiplicative SMILES-based optimal descriptors	Linear Model	Shared with: Lab of Process Control and Informatics	May 5, 2019
Test Periklis	model	This is a test and more to see if it will be updated Shared with: Lab of Process Control and Informatics	Mar 14, 2019

At the bottom right of the interface, there is a status bar showing "Home", "near nano", "1 - 4 of 4", and navigation icons.

Figure 39. Search results on the Jaqpot GUI

8. Semantic query and text mining

In the last section of this deliverable, we present approaches provided as part of the NanoCommons KB to extract data and information from the scientific literature. The text mining tools are included in the Komenti software. It combines semantic ontology query tools with natural language processing technologies to enable nanomaterials concept data mining using the eNanoMapper ontology. This section will describe how to install, and use these tools. It culminates in practical examples of summarising the relationship between a nanomaterial and toxicity concepts in the literature, and ontology axiom suggestion from text mined annotations of class metadata. Work is ongoing to further integrate the tools as services accessible within the KB and the integration of the extracted data into the knowledge warehouse (as literature mined datasets).

8.1. Installation and Setup

The following software is required:

- Groovy
 - <http://groovy-lang.org/>
 - Commands tested on Groovy Version: 2.5.8 JVM: 1.8.0_232 Vendor: Oracle Corporation OS: Linux
- Git
 - <https://git-scm.com/>

Commands should be able to run in any command line interface, including on the Windows terminal emulator. However, commands in this document were tested on a Bash console on Linux.

Once these software packages are installed, the following command can be used to obtain the software, and change into the directory of the script.

```
$ git clone https://github.com/reality/komenti
$ cd komenti
```

The other packages and libraries necessary will be downloaded automatically when the script is first run. This may take some time on a slower Internet connection (and will not produce any output while the download is on-going), as the Stanford CoreNLP models files are large.

8.2. Semantic Querying and Label Expansion

The Komenti software allows for the download of classes and class labels, via semantic queries from the AberOWL ontology repository.

```
$ ./Komenti query -o ENM -q "nanoparticle and has_component_part some
'barium sulfete'" --out labels.txt
```

This command queries the EL reasoner which underlies AberOWL, to find class definitions which are equivalent to, or subclasses of, the class intentionally defined by the query provided. In this case, *labels.txt* will contain the following:

Label	IRI ¹¹	Group
nm-220	http://purl.enanomapper.org/onto/ENM_9000240	nanoparticle and has_component_part some 'barium sulfate'
baso4 nanoparticle	http://purl.enanomapper.org/onto/ENM_9000240	nanoparticle and has_component_part some 'barium sulfate'

For each label (including synonyms and alternative terms defined in the ontology) associated with each returned class, a line with the textual label, the IRI (which uniquely identifies the class), and the query used to return the class is listed. Even outside of the context of the rest of this application, the function remains useful as an interface for querying the ontology using description logic.

A list of class labels can also be queried using the *-c/--class-list* parameter.

```
$ ./Komenti query -o ENM -c toxicity,asbestos --out labels.txt
```

Importantly for text mining functionality, subclasses are returned, but retain the 'group' of their parent. For example, in the results for the above query, the entry for *carcinogenicity* would be:

Label	IRI	Group
carcinogenicity	http://purl.enanomapper.org/onto/ENM_0000029	toxicity

To facilitate improved vocabularies for named entity recognition tasks, the query command can also expand the list of labels with word stems, using the *-e/--expand-labels* argument. The query expansion also includes some custom mappings for the purpose of matching nanomaterials (for example, toxicity to toxic, and removing 'nanoparticle' from labels).

8.3. Abstract Download

¹¹ Internationalized Resource Identifier: similar to a Universal Resource Identifier but extended to the *Universal Coded Character Set*.

Using the labels produced by the *query* command, abstracts can be downloaded from PubMed Central. The EBI PMC API is used first to query full text articles for the relevant labels, and then to download the articles, populating the output directory. The API is documented here: <https://europepmc.org/RestfulWebService>

```
$ ./Komenti get_abstracts -l labels.txt --out articles/
```

By default, queries will be grouped by IRI. So, for the *labels.txt* that contains *ENM_9000240*, the query will be:

```
("nm-220" OR "baso4 nanoparticle")
```

For each distinct class in the labels file, such a disjunctive query (the two sets of search terms joined with the AND operator) will be run, containing each of its labels. Alternatively, queries can be grouped by the query that was used to retrieve them with the *--group-by-query* command. For example, the *labels.txt* file produced by the *toxicity,asbestos* class list will produce the following query for asbestos, as well as another subsequent query containing the labels for toxicity:

```
("actinolite asbestos" OR "amosite asbestos" OR "amphibole asbestos" OR  
"anthophyllite asbestos" OR "asbestos" OR "chrysotile" OR "crocidolite  
asbestos" OR "serpentine asbestos" OR "tremolite asbestos")
```

In either case, each group's query is run in series, essentially constituting a logical disjunction. Using the *--conjunction* argument, the groups can be queried with a logical conjunction. For example, the following command:

```
$ ./Komenti get_abstracts -l labels.txt --group-by-query --conjunction --out  
out/articles/
```

would, for a *labels.txt* produced by a *query* command that acquired labels for *fullerene* and *asbestos*, produce the following single query:

```
("c60 fullerene" OR "(c60-ih)[5,6]fullerene" OR "c70 fullerene" OR "(c70-  
d5h(6))[5,6]fullerene" OR "fullerene" OR "fullerenes" OR "fullerenol  
nanoparticle") AND ("actinolite asbestos" OR "amosite asbestos" OR "amphibole  
asbestos" OR "anthophyllite asbestos" OR "asbestos" OR "chrysotile" OR  
"crocidolite asbestos" OR "serpentine asbestos" OR "tremolite asbestos")
```

The difference is that with a disjunctive query articles will be downloaded that mention each label group, while for the conjunctive query, only articles that mention every label group will be

downloaded.

The library currently only supports the download of 1000 articles at a time. The `-l/--limit` parameter can further limit the maximum number of articles that can be downloaded. If the `--lemmatise` parameter is used, the downloaded text will be lemmatised (grouping together so that they can be analysed as a single item).

8.4. Metadata Download

The tool can also be used to download metadata about classes. This includes any associated annotation properties, such as database cross-references, labels, and descriptions.

```
$ ./Komenti get_metadata -l out/labels.txt --out ls/
```

This command will query AberOWL for each class in the labels file, and create a file containing the information associated with it. For example, the 'fullerene.txt' file in the output directory would contain the following text:

```
owlClass: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CHEBI\_33416>
class: http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CHEBI\_33416
ontology: ENM
deprecated: false
synonyms:
  fullerenes
  fullerene
id:
  CHEBI:33416
has_related_synonym:
  Fulleren
  fulerenos
  fullerenos
  fullereno
  fulereno
__obo__:
  chebi_ontology
has_obo_namespace:
  chebi_ontology
disease_ontology:
  chebi_ontology
label: fullerene
definition:
  A compound composed solely of an even number of carbon atoms, which form a cage-like fused-ring polycyclic system with twelve five-membered rings and the rest six-membered rings. The term has been broadened to include any
```

```
closed cage structure consisting entirely of three-coordinate carbon atoms.
```

It also shares many of the same arguments as the `get_metadata` command, such as `--limit` and `--lemmatise`. It does not include the query formation modifiers, such as `--conjunction`, as the command retrieves information for each class directly from the ontology via AberOWL.

8.5. Annotation and Labelling

Labels acquired by the `query` command can be used to annotate text, using Stanford CoreNLP.

In this case, we will use a `labels.txt` containing classes and labels pertaining to fullerene and toxicity, produced by the following command:

```
$ ./Komenti query -c fullerene,toxicity -o ENM --expand-labels --out labels.txt
```

We will create the file `PMC6037823.txt`, populating it with the following abstract, from Freixa et al. (2018).

```
Organic micro-contaminants (OMCs) enter in freshwaters and interact with other contaminants such as carbon nanoparticles, becoming a problem of unknown consequences for river ecosystems. Carbon nanoparticles (as fullerenes C60) are good adsorbents of organic contaminants and their interaction can potentially affect their toxicity to river biofilms. We tested the C60 interactions with selected OMCs and their effects on river biofilms in different short-term experiments. In these, river biofilms were exposed to C60 and three OMCs (triclosan, diuron, or venlafaxine) and their respective mixtures with fullerenes (C60 + each OMC). The effects were evaluated on structural, molecular, and functional descriptors of river biofilms. Our results showed that C60 did not cause toxic effects in river biofilms, whereas diuron and triclosan significantly affected the heterotrophic and phototrophic components of biofilms and venlafaxine affected only the phototrophic component. The joint exposure of C60 with venlafaxine was not producing differences with respect to the former response of the toxicant, but the overall response was antagonistic (i.e., decreased toxicity) with diuron, and synergistic (i.e., increased toxicity) with triclosan. We suggest that differences in the toxic responses could be related to the respective molecular structure of each OMC, to the concentration proportion between OMC and C60, and to the possible competition between C60 pollutants on blocking the receptors of the biological cell membranes. We conclude that the presence of C60 at low concentrations modified the toxicity of OMC to river biofilms. These interactions should therefore be considered when predicting toxicity of OMC in river ecosystems.
```

D4.6 Description of tools for automated data mining

As can be seen, the abstract describes a paper that investigates the effects of carbon nanoparticles on the toxic effects of organic micro-contaminants on river biofilms.

```
$ ./Komenti annotate -l out/labels.txt -t PMC6037823.txt --out out/annotations.txt
```

This command produces an *annotations.txt* file, with the following content (the sentence column is omitted in this document, but would normally contain the text of the sentence).

File	Class	Sentence ID	Tags
PMC6037823.txt	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CHEBI_33416	2	
PMC6037823.txt	http://purl.bioontology.org/ontology/npo#NPO_1338	2	uncertain
PMC6037823.txt	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CHEBI_33416	4	
PMC6037823.txt	http://purl.bioontology.org/ontology/npo#NPO_1338	6	negated
PMC6037823.txt	http://purl.bioontology.org/ontology/npo#NPO_1338	7	Negated, uncertain
PMC6037823.txt	http://purl.bioontology.org/ontology/npo#NPO_1338	8	
PMC6037823.txt	http://purl.bioontology.org/ontology/npo#NPO_1338	9	
PMC6037823.txt	http://purl.bioontology.org/ontology/npo#NPO_1338	10	uncertain

This constitutes an annotation of entities from *labels.txt* in the abstract, per sentence. Additionally, the tags *negated* and *uncertain* indicate whether or not the entity was explicitly negated, or expressed in uncertain terms in the sentence. This provides more semantic information about the context in which the concept was mentioned.

The *--text/-t* parameter can also be passed to a directory, in which all files will be annotated.

8.6. Automating Mining Pipelines

The results of each command discussed previously can be used in series, as part of a natural language processing pipeline. First, collecting the labels of relevant entities, and annotating text with them. To run entire pipelines for a particular query at once, rosters can be generated by the application, describing a series of arguments of the Komenti program.

```
$ ./Komenti gen_roster --with-abstracts-download --query "toxicity" --  
ontology ENM --out roster.json
```

This will create a *roster.json* file with the following content.

```
{  
  "commands": [  
    {  
      "command": "query",  
      "args": {  
        "ontology": "HP",  
        "query": "toxicity",  
        "out": "./out/labels.txt",  
        "expand-labels": true  
      }  
    },  
    {  
      "command": "get_abstracts",  
      "args": {  
        "labels": "./out/labels.txt",  
        "out": "./out/abstracts/"  
      }  
    },  
    {  
      "command": "annotate",  
      "args": {  
        "text": "./out/abstracts/",  
        "labels": "./out/labels.txt",  
        "out": "./out/annotations.txt"  
      }  
    }  
  ]  
}
```

This describes running the query, get_abstracts, and annotate command for the query 'toxicity' in series. The *--with-abstract-download* parameter can be omitted, in which case you must provide the *-t/--text* parameter specifying a file or directory to annotate.

The roster can be run using the following command:

```
$ ./Komenti auto -r roster.json
```

Rosters can also be created manually, by copying and editing a template from the *templates/* subdirectory.

8.7. Concept Relationship Summaries

The software can be used to mine relationships between two groups of concepts in the eNanoMapper ontology.

```
$ ./Komenti gen_roster --mine-relationship -c asbestos,toxicity -o ENM --out enm_roster.json
```

This will obtain labels for toxicity and asbestos, then download abstracts mentioning both, and annotate them. After this, it will run a final command, *summarise_entity_pair*, which produces the following output from the annotation file:

```
asbestos is mentioned 919 times
toxicity is mentioned 564 times
Considered 371 documents and 1483 annotations
asbestos and toxicity are mentioned together 581 times.
  crocidolite asbestos and toxicity (18 mentions, 6 articles, 5 uncertain, 3
negated)
  asbestos and toxicity (223 mentions, 40 articles, 85 uncertain, 18
negated)
  asbestos and carcinogenicity (107 mentions, 17 articles, 34 uncertain, 21
negated)
  amosite asbestos and carcinogenicity (3 mentions, 1 articles, 0 uncertain,
1 negated)
  asbestos and genetic toxicity (29 mentions, 8 articles, 7 uncertain, 8
negated)
  chrysotile and cytotoxicity (13 mentions, 5 articles, 2 uncertain, 0
negated)
  chrysotile and mutagenicity (7 mentions, 2 articles, 0 uncertain, 0
negated)
  chrysotile and carcinogenicity (21 mentions, 5 articles, 10 uncertain, 12
negated)
  asbestos and cytotoxicity (57 mentions, 15 articles, 20 uncertain, 2
negated)
  chrysotile and inhalation toxicity (6 mentions, 1 articles, 3 uncertain, 1
negated)
  amphibole asbestos and inhalation toxicity (5 mentions, 1 articles, 1
```

```

uncertain, 0 negated)
  asbestos and mutagenicity (34 mentions, 4 articles, 15 uncertain, 0
negated)
  amosite asbestos and cytotoxicity (2 mentions, 1 articles, 0 uncertain, 1
negated)
  chrysotile and toxicity (34 mentions, 5 articles, 3 uncertain, 1 negated)
  serpentine asbestos and toxicity (1 mentions, 1 articles, 1 uncertain, 0
negated)
  amphibole asbestos and toxicity (2 mentions, 1 articles, 1 uncertain, 0
negated)
  amphibole asbestos and mutagenicity (5 mentions, 1 articles, 4 uncertain,
0 negated)
  amphibole asbestos and carcinogenicity (2 mentions, 1 articles, 0
uncertain, 0 negated)
  crocidolite asbestos and carcinogenicity (1 mentions, 1 articles, 1
uncertain, 0 negated)
  crocidolite asbestos and cytotoxicity (3 mentions, 1 articles, 0
uncertain, 0 negated)
  crocidolite asbestos and genetic toxicity (6 mentions, 1 articles, 2
uncertain, 0 negated)
  amphibole asbestos and genetic toxicity (2 mentions, 1 articles, 0
uncertain, 0 negated)
  
```

In this way, we can see that by using the pipeline, we can gain a summary of the relationship between different subclasses of nanoparticles and different kinds of toxicity. In this case, particularly, we see what kinds of toxicity are discussed around what kinds of asbestos in the literature available via PMC. By further analysing the annotations, additional insight may be gained into these relationships.

8.8. Axiom Suggestion

Another use for the text mining pipeline is to suggest new axioms for classes.

```

$ ./Komenti gen_roster --suggest-axiom --with-metadata-download -c
'nanoparticle' --ontology ENM --entity
nanoparticle,nanocage,nanocell,nanosphere,nanohorn,nanorod,nanotube,nanoshel
l,'quantum dot' --default-entity nanoparticle --quality 'chemical
substance','environmental material' --default-relation has_component_part --
out enm_roster.json
  
```

When run with *Komenti auto*, the roster, that the above command produces, will perform the following steps:

1. Populate the labels.txt file with (all classes or object properties from the eNanoMapper ontology):
 - a. Subclasses of *nanoparticle* with the group *classes*

- b. The classes *nanoparticle*, *nanocage*, *nanocell*, *nanosphere*, *nanohorn*, *nanorod*, *nanotube*, *nanoshell*, *quantum dot* with the group *entity*.
 - c. Subclasses of the classes *environmental material* and *chemical substance* with the group *entity*.
 - d. All object properties with the group *relation*.
2. Download metadata for every class in group *classes*
 3. Annotate the metadata
 4. Mine axioms from the annotations

In effect, the roster will produce axiom suggestions of the form *Entity and (Relation some Quality)* for all subclasses of *nanoparticle* in the eNanoMapper ontology, by mining the metadata of the classes in the ontology for associations between the groups of classes. The following example describes the suggestion produced for the *metal nanoparticle* class.

```
Suggested axiom for metal nanoparticle
(http://purl.bioontology.org/ontology/npo#NPO_1384):
nanoparticle AND (has_component_part SOME metallic material)
<http://purl.bioontology.org/ontology/npo#NPO_707> AND
(<http://purl.enomapper.org/onto/internal/npo-ext.owl#has_component_part> SOME
<http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/ENVO_01001069>)
```

Evidence:
metal nanoparticle.txt:1

The suggested axiom is given in Manchester OWL Syntax, both using the first label of the classes matched, and their IRIs. Evidence is given with respect to the incremental sentence ID of annotated files the matched classes were found in.

Instead of the ENM ontology, RO (referring to the Relation Ontology) could be passed via the argument *--relation-ontology* to explore a greater variety of relationships. Additionally, *--entity-ontology* could be set to CHEBI, to search for chemical qualities that are not currently imported into the ENM ontology. Classes, qualities, entities, and relations can be acquired in more complex ways (e.g. from multiple queries and ontologies) by editing the roster file manually to add additional query blocks. Pubmed abstracts can also be mined for axioms, by using *--with-abstracts-download* instead of *--with-metadata-download*, and other texts can be provided via the *--text* argument.

8.9. Searching with identifiers

The above examples search by textual labels. A complementary approach is the use of identifiers in written materials (journal articles, report, project deliverables, etc). This has been common practice for genes, particularly human genes, where HGNC identifiers are used, and for protein crystal structures where PDB identifiers are common. For example, we can also search with the JRC representative material identifiers, such as JRCNM01005a (see also [these ontology mappings](#)):

```
./Komenti query -o ENM -c JRCNM01005a --out labels.txt
```

For similar reasons, we have set up an identifier registry for yet undisclosed nanomaterials and nanomaterials for which no data is released yet: the [European Registry of Materials](#). Research projects can use this registry to get unique, global identifiers for the materials they study, without having to disclose any information yet. At the same time, in written material they can use these identifiers. Recommended here is reporting them as compact identifiers (Wimalaratne et al. 2018).

Previously, the ContentMine software has been used to recognize JRC nanomaterials in full texts (<https://github.com/egonw/cmnanotox>). This resulted in annotation of those articles in Wikidata with the items for these nanomaterials (see Waagmeester et al. 2019). This allows making an [overview of literature for the JRC materials possible](#). However, while the NanoSafety Cluster has published several hundreds of research papers, few of them use identifiers consistently. Indeed, only eighteen publications have appeared since 2017 on the JRC representative nanomaterials (Figure 40), as analyzed here with Scholia (Nielsen et al. 2017, Rasberry et al. 2019):

Publications per year

Figure 40. Overview on literature for JRC materials

Nevertheless, recognizing by their identifiers is easy and can be automated. Researchers, at the same time, can use the Scholia server Rich Site Summary (RSS) news feeds functionality (Figure 41) to follow new publications in, for example, Feedly¹².

¹² <https://feedly.com/>

D4.6 Description of tools for automated data mining

Recently published works on the chemical

Show entries Search:

Date	Work	Type	Topics
2019-11-22	Applicability and Limitations in the Characterization of Poly-Dispersed Engineered Nanomaterials in Cell Media by Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS)	scholarly article	JRCNM02000a // JRCNM02102a // JRCNM01001a
2019-10-18	Polystyrene nanoplastics disrupt glucose metabolism and cortisol levels with a possible link to behavioural changes in larval zebrafish	scholarly article	JRCNM01005a // glucose metabolic process // cortisol // Danio rerio
2019-08-08	The variances in cytokine production profiles from non- or activated THP-1, Kupffer cell and human blood derived primary macrophages following exposure to either alcohol or a panel of engineered nanomaterials	scholarly article	cytokine // JRCNM01101a // JRCNM01005a // macrophage
2019-07-28	Protein and lipid homeostasis altered in rat macrophages after exposure to metallic oxide nanoparticles	scholarly article	JRCNM01100a // macrophage // homeostasis // Rattus // protein // lipid
2019-05-13	The importance of inter-individual Kupffer cell variability in the governance of hepatic toxicity in a 3D primary human liver microtissue model	scholarly article	governance // JRCNM01101a // JRCNM01005a
2019-03-29	Corbicula fluminea gene expression modulated by CeO2 nanomaterials and salinity	scholarly article	JRCNM02102a // Corbicula fluminea // salinity // gene expression
2019-01-03	Interaction of biologically relevant proteins with ZnO nanomaterials: A	scholarly	toxicity // JRCNM01101a // JRCNM01100a

Figure 41. Use of Scholia server Rich Site Summary (RSS) news feeds functionality.

In Feedly, new articles in Wikidata about the JRC materials will show up as shown in the screenshot in Figure 42.

Scholia - Latest Articles for Q47461491 ✓ ≡ ↻ ...

1 follower / 1 article per week

LATEST

	Applicability and Limitations in the Characterization of Poly-Dispersed Engineered Nanomaterials in Cell Media by Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS)	Chiara Riganti, Elisabetta Aldieri, Riccardo Leinardi, C	23min
	Polystyrene nanoplastics disrupt glucose metabolism and cortisol levels with a possible link to behavioural changes in larval zebrafish	Nadja R Brun, Martina G Vijver, Christian Tudorache	2d
	The variances in cytokine production profiles from non- or activated THP-1, Kupffer cell and human blood derived primary macrophages following exposure to either alcohol or a panel of engineered nanomaterials		3mo
	Protein and lipid homeostasis altered in rat macrophages after exposure to metallic oxide nanoparticles	[no content]	3mo
	The importance of inter-individual Kupffer cell variability in the governance of hepatic toxicity in a 3D primary human liver microtissue model	[no content]	3mo
	Corbicula fluminea gene expression modulated by CeO2 nanomaterials and salinity	[no content]	3mo
	Interaction of biologically relevant proteins with ZnO nanomaterials: A confounding factor for in vitro toxicity endpoints	Anders Baun, Anders Baun	3mo
	Fish cell lines as a tool for the ecotoxicity assessment and ranking of engineered nanomaterials	[no content]	25mo
	Graphistrength® C100 MultiWalled Carbon Nanotubes (MWCNT): thirteen-week inhalation toxicity study in rats with 13- and 52-week recovery periods combined with comet and micronucleus assays	[no content]	30mo
	Elucidating the Role of Dissolution in CeO2	[no content]	31mo
	Negligible cytotoxicity induced by different titanium dioxide nanoparticles in fish cell lines.	[no content]	35mo
	The JRC Nanomaterials Repository: A unique facility providing representative test materials for nanoEHS research	[no content]	37mo
	Towards the standardization of nanoeotoxicity testing: Natural organic matter 'camouflages' the adverse effects of TiO2 and CeO2 nanoparticles on green microalgae.	Gotzone Barandika, Gotzone Barandika	49mo
	Lung inflammation and lack of genotoxicity in the comet and micronucleus assays of industrial multiwalled carbon nanotubes Graphistrength(®) C100 after a 90-day nose-only inhalation exposure of rats	[no content]	53mo

Figure 42. New articles in Wikidata about JRC test nanomaterials.

Moreover, annotation with other topics allows the user to explore related topics, as defined by the scope of the articles. Scholia shows a network of topics, where the edges reflect the occurrence in the same article, as shown in Figure 43.

D4.6 Description of tools for automated data mining

Figure 43. Network of topics, where the edges reflect the occurrence in the same article.

9. Conclusions

Deliverable 4.6 presents the various tools for automated data, model and text mining that have been developed and integrated in the NanoCommons research infrastructure. We reported how the tools developed enable users from the community to perform, through automated procedures, tasks critical to nanoinformatics: When a research idea has already been formed, the NanoCommons tools accompany the user over each stage, starting from searches of the NanoCommons KB to retrieve data, continuing with similarity-focused exploration of the data retrieved in order to increase the validity of data and support data analysis, building on the data to generate, publish and communicate models in a platform that provides the capability to search within available models for the ones meeting the desired user-defined criteria. NanoCommons also supports very early stages of knowledge exploration and idea formulation. The user is provided with the capability to employ ontologies for synonym identification and for mining of scientific literature in order to pinpoint relevant existing knowledge. Coordinated use of the automated tools offered by NanoCommons provides a great enhancement to the capacity of the community to advance knowledge on nanomaterials environmental health and safety and nanomaterials risk assessment .

10. References

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Appendix 1. Python functions developed for the NanoCommons similarity search tool

Convert strings to numerical features / categories

```
def all_numerical(df):
    dfs = df.select_dtypes(include=['object'])
    df_numeric = df.select_dtypes(exclude=['object'])
    dfsc = pd.DataFrame()
    string_maps = []
    for val in list(dfs):
        if dfs[val].isnull().values.any() == False:
            i = 0
            uniques = np.unique(dfs[val])
            u, indices = np.unique(dfs[val], return_index=True)
            if val == 'Id':
                ids = {}
                for i in range(len(indices)):
                    ids[u[i]] = indices[i]
            data = np.searchsorted(uniques, dfs[val])
            dft = pd.Series(data).rename(val)
            df_numeric[val] = dft.values
            dicts = {}
            for i in range(len(u)):
                dicts[u[i]] = dft.loc[indices[i]]
            string_maps.append({val:dicts})
    qj = {}
    for key in list(df_numeric):
        qj[key] = None
    return df_numeric, ids ,qj, string_maps
```

Prepare the query

```
def prepare_query(df):
    df, ids, qj, dicts = all_numerical(df)
    print("String have been converted to unique integers as follows: ")
    for di in dicts:
        print(di)
    print("Import the query values needed on the following object: ")
    print(qj)
    prepare_query(df)
```

Similarity search function

```
def similarity_search(df, query_dict, metric, bring):
    search_for = []
    for key in query_dict:
        search_for.append(key)
    dfn, ids, qj, dicts = all_numerical(df)
    sdf = dfn[search_for].dropna()
    query_dict_for_df = {}
    for key in query_dict:
        query_dict_for_df[key] = [query_dict[key]]
    search_for_dataset = pd.DataFrame.from_dict(query_dict_for_df)
    if metric is not None:
        pwd = pairwise_distances(search_for_dataset, sdf, metric=metric)
    else:
        pwd = pairwise_distances(search_for_dataset, sdf)
    indexes = sdf.index.values.astype(int)
    df_shorted = pd.DataFrame()
    pwd_length = len(pwd[0])
    pwdm = pwd[0]
    mins_shorted = []
    for i in range(pwd_length):
        minElement = np.amin(pwdm)
        result = np.where(pwdm == np.amin(pwdm))
        pwdm = np.delete(pwdm, result[0][0], 0)
        mins_shorted.append(minElement)
    ind_uniq = []
    for s in mins_shorted:
        ind = np.where(pwd[0] == s)
        for indi in ind[0]:
            if indi in ind_uniq:
                continue
            else:
                ind_uniq.append(indi)
    df_similar = pd.DataFrame(columns=list(df))
    ids = []
    for indic in ind_uniq:
        df_similar.append(df.loc[[indic]])
        ids.append(df.loc[[indic]]['Id'])
    return ids[:bring], mins_shorted[:bring]
```

Appendix 2. Definition of distance metrics in the NanoCommons similarity search tool

The following tables list the string metric identifiers and the associated distance metric classes. Assuming that x and y are the vectors containing selected variables from the fingerprints representing two nanomaterials, the various metrics are defined as follows¹³:

Metrics intended for real-valued vector spaces:

Identifier	Class name	Arguments	Distance function
"euclidean"	EuclideanDistance	-	$\sqrt{\sum((x - y)^2)}$
"manhattan"	ManhattanDistance	-	$\sum(x - y)$
"chebyshev"	ChebyshevDistance	-	$\max(x - y)$
"minkowski"	MinkowskiDistance	p	$\sum(x - y ^p)^{1/p}$
"wminkowski"	WMinkowskiDistance	p, w	$\sum(w * (x - y) ^p)^{1/p}$
"seuclidean"	SEuclideanDistance	V	$\sqrt{\sum((x - y)^2 / V)}$
"mahalanobis"	MahalanobisDistance	V or VI	$\sqrt{(x - y)' V^{-1} (x - y)}$

Metrics intended for integer-valued vector spaces: Though intended for integer-valued vectors, these are also valid metrics in the case of real-valued vectors.

Identifier	Class name	Distance function
"hamming"	HammingDistance	$N_{\text{unequal}}(x, y) / N_{\text{tot}}$

¹³ More detailed information on the distance metrics within scikit-learn can be found at <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.neighbors.DistanceMetric.html>

D4.6 Description of tools for automated data mining

"canberra"	CanberraDistance	$\text{sum}(x - y / (x + y))$
"braycurtis"	BrayCurtisDistance	$\text{sum}(x - y) / (\text{sum}(x) + \text{sum}(y))$

Metrics intended for boolean-valued vector spaces: Any nonzero entry is evaluated to "True". In the listings below, the following abbreviations are used:

- **N** : number of dimensions
- **NTT** : number of dimensions in which both values are True
- **NTF** : number of dimensions in which the first value is True, second is False
- **NFT** : number of dimensions in which the first value is False, second is True
- **NFF** : number of dimensions in which both values are False
- **NNEQ** : number of non-equal dimensions, $\text{NNEQ} = \text{NTF} + \text{NFT}$
- **NNZ** : number of nonzero dimensions, $\text{NNZ} = \text{NTF} + \text{NFT} + \text{NTT}$

Identifier	Class name	Distance function
"jaccard"	JaccardDistance	NNEQ / NNZ
"matching"	MatchingDistance	NNEQ / N
"dice"	DiceDistance	$\text{NNEQ} / (\text{NTT} + \text{NNZ})$
"kulsinski"	KulsinskiDistance	$(\text{NNEQ} + \text{N} - \text{NTT}) / (\text{NNEQ} + \text{N})$
"rogerstanimoto"	RogersTanimotoDistance	$2 * \text{NNEQ} / (\text{N} + \text{NNEQ})$
"russellrao"	RussellRaoDistance	NNZ / N
"sokalmichener"	SokalMichenerDistance	$2 * \text{NNEQ} / (\text{N} + \text{NNEQ})$
"sokalsneath"	SokalSneathDistance	$\text{NNEQ} / (\text{NNEQ} + 0.5 * \text{NTT})$